

Universidade do Minho
Escola de Engenharia

Oxana Barsukova
**AI and Photogrammetry for HBIM: Automating
Historic Building Classification and Modelling**

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Automating Historic Building
Classification and Modelling**

European Master in
Building Information Modelling

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European Master in
Building Information Modelling

Master Dissertation
European Master in Building Information Modelling

Work conducted under supervision of:

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October, 2025

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STATEMENT OF INTEGRITY

I hereby declare having conducted this academic work with integrity. I confirm that I have not used plagiarism or any form of undue use of information or falsification of results along the process leading to its elaboration.

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RESUMO

O uso do Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM) tornou-se cada vez mais relevante para a documentação e conservação da arquitetura histórica. Apesar das suas vantagens, um dos principais desafios reside na transformação dos dados de levantamento em modelos estruturados, um processo que continua a ser predominantemente manual e demorado, sobretudo quando aplicado a alvenarias de pedra complexas. Este estudo explora o potencial da inteligência artificial (IA) para melhorar e automatizar parcialmente o fluxo de trabalho do HBIM, com especial enfoque nos edifícios românicos em Portugal.

A investigação introduz uma abordagem combinada baseada em imagens e em nuvens de pontos. Fotografias de fachadas em alta resolução foram segmentadas através de métodos de aprendizagem profunda, incluindo U-Net e o Segment Anything Model (SAM), para identificar unidades de alvenaria, juntas de argamassa e vãos. Estas segmentações em 2D foram posteriormente transferidas para o espaço 3D através da calibração de câmaras no COLMAP, gerando nuvens de pontos enriquecidas com rótulos semânticos.

Os resultados indicam que o fluxo de trabalho proposto permite a criação de conjuntos de dados semanticamente estruturados que podem ser incorporados em ambientes HBIM, oferecendo uma alternativa mais eficiente ao modelação manual convencional. Embora persistam limitações — como a reduzida dimensão do conjunto de dados, a generalização dos modelos de IA e a ausência de protocolos totalmente normalizados para dados patrimoniais — a abordagem demonstra a viabilidade da integração da IA nas práticas de documentação do património. Ao ligar a segmentação de imagens em 2D à classificação em 3D, este estudo contribui para os esforços em curso de automatização da documentação patrimonial e oferece novas perspetivas para aplicações HBIM escaláveis, precisas e ricas em informação.

Palavras chave: Inteligência Artificial (IA), Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM), edifícios patrimoniais Românicos, processo Scan-to-HBIM (digitalização para HBIM), segmentação

ABSTRACT

The use of Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM) has become increasingly relevant for the documentation and conservation of historic architecture. Despite its advantages, one of the major challenges lies in transforming survey data into structured models, a process that is still predominantly manual and time-consuming, especially when applied to complex stone masonry. This study explores the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance and partially automate HBIM workflow, with a particular focus on Romanesque heritage buildings in Portugal.

The research introduces a combined image- and point cloud-based approach. High-resolution façade photos were segmented using deep learning methods, including U-Net and the Segment Anything Model (SAM), to identify masonry units, mortar joints, and openings. These 2D segmentations were subsequently transferred into 3D space through COLMAP camera calibration, generating point clouds enriched with semantic labels.

Findings indicate that the proposed workflow allows the creation of semantically structured datasets that can be incorporated into HBIM environments, providing a more efficient alternative to conventional manual modelling. Although limitations persist - such as small dataset size, generalisation of AI models, and the absence of fully standardised heritage data protocols - the approach demonstrates the feasibility of integrating AI into c practices. By linking 2D image segmentation with 3D classification, this study contributes to ongoing efforts to automate heritage documentation and offers new perspectives for scalable, accurate, and information-rich HBIM applications.

Keywords: AI, HBIM, Romanesque heritage buildings, Scan-to-HBIM, Segmentation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1. HBIM: CONCEPTS, HBIM USES, STANDARDIZATION CHALLENGES.....	4
2.2. EXISTING SCAN-TO-HBIM WORKFLOWS.....	13
2.3. AUTOMATION IN SCAN-TO-HBIM: STRATEGIES AND TECHNIQUES.....	18
2.4. SUMMARY AND IDENTIFIED GAPS.....	29
3. CASE STUDY PROPOSAL	31
3.1. OBJECT OF STUDY.....	31
3.1.1. Historical Background of the Building.....	31
3.1.2. Architectural and Technical Characteristics.....	32
3.1.3. Summary of Available Information.....	35
3.2. APPLIED METHODOLOGY.....	36
3.2.1. Objectives and Scope.....	36
3.2.2. Background and Rationale.....	36
3.2.3. Justification of Methods.....	36
3.2.4. Comparison with Literature Methods.....	48
3.2.5. Limitations of the Study.....	48
4. RESULTS	49
4.1. CONTEXTUALIZATION AND OVERVIEW.....	49
4.2. PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF KEY FINDINGS.....	49
4.3. LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES.....	53
4.4. IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS WORKS.....	54
5. CONCLUSIONS	55
REFERENCES.....	57
APPENDICES.....	62
APPENDIX 1: dataset.py (pairing, resizing, normalization)	62
APPENDIX 2: model.py (UNet).....	64
APPENDIX 3: train.py (training loop, losses, AMP, checkpoints, visualizations).....	65
APPENDIX 4: inference.py (prediction to raw IDs/color masks).....	71
APPENDIX 5: evaluate.py (IoU metrics).....	72
APPENDIX 6: generate_masks_sam.py.....	73
APPENDIX 7: project_masks_to_pointcloud.py.....	79

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 – HBIM Uses and the HBIM Goals they support with an indication of which BIM	5
Figure 2 – BIM Uses in identified cases of HBIM methodology implementation	5
Figure 3 – Connection of identified uses groups to EIR, MPDT, BEP documents	6
Figure 4 – Workflow of HBIM	8
Figure 5 – Data Acquisition techniques in HBIM	8
Figure 6 – Factors influencing a TLS measurement	9
Figure 7 – Limitations and challenges adapted from Liu et al. (2023)	9
Figure 8 – 16 LODs based on façade geometry grades	11
Figure 9 – Logical organization of the database	13
Figure 10 – Diagram describing the manual construction method of HBIM library	14
Figure 11 – Example of thematic map of the material decay and related descriptive legend	15
Figure 12 – Different types of Machine Learning systems	18
Figure 13 – The colors of the segmentation indicate the different classes	24
Figure 14 – Methodological Workflow which combines Colour-based segmentation	24
Figure 15 – From left to right: biological colonization and unaltered...	25
Figure 16 – ArCH dataset	28
Figure 17 – The methodology for synthetic data adoption	29
Figure 18 – Archive data of São João de Calvos church	31
Figure 19 – Location of São João de Calvos church	32
Figure 20 – Failure mechanisms in Romanesque churches	33
Figure 21 – Shear mechanism identified on architrave	34
Figure 22– Ultrasonic velocity ratio of stone masonry	34
Figure 23 – Wall infills/mortar fillings	34
Figure 24 – Ultrasonic survey	35
Figure 25 – Point cloud created in Agisoft Metashape	38
Figure 26 – Orthogonal façade images S. João de Calvos	38

Figure 27 – Ground truth annotation masks created in CVAT and Photoshop	39
Figure 28 – Grayscale masks with class IDs	40
Figure 29 –Masks created from varied sources to train UNet	40
Figure 30 – The U-Net architecture	41
Figure 31 – Monitoring semantic segmentation with UNet	42
Figure 32 – Training command	43
Figure 33 – Evaluation command	43
Figure 34 – Inference command	43
Figure 35– Workflow applied for stone segmentation	44
Figure 36 – Example of autosegmentation in SAM	44
Figure 37 – Example of online segmentation in SAM platform	45
Figure 38 – Automatically created masks with 2 Classes	46
Figure 39 – Relationship between AI, ML,NN, and DL	49
Figure 40 – Visualization of 34 Epochs with graphs during the training process of UNet	50
Figure 41 – Visualization of epoch overlay (14, 16 and 26 epochs)	51
Figure 42 – Difference in results obtained from both UNet and SAM approaches	52
Figure 43 – Result of 2D SAM masks projection onto Point clouds	53

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – National standards and local practices applied for HBIM in varied countries	10
Table 2 – Comparative analysis of masonry morphological characteristics and segmentation methods in similar case studies	17
Table 3 – Semi-Automated Scan to HBIM	20
Table 4 – Fully Automated Scan to HBIM	25
Table 5 – Overview of Photographic Survey Equipment and Number of Images	37
Table 6 – The total number of correct masks generated by SAM	45

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AEC	Architecture Engineering and Construction
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	American Institute of Architects
AR	Augmented Reality
ARXIV	Preprint server for scientific papers
BEP	BIM Execution Plan
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BLK360	Leica BLK360 terrestrial laser scanner
B-Rep	Boundary Representation
CDE	Common Data Environment
CLAHE	Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COLMAP	Structure from Motion photogrammetry software
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CVAT	Computer Vision Annotation Tool
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DGCNN	Dynamic Graph Convolutional Neural Network
DGEMN	Direção-Geral dos Edifícios e Monumentos Nacionais (Portuguese heritage agency)
DJI	Drone manufacturer (DJI)
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
EIR	Exchange Information Requirements
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GOG	Grade of Generation (HBIM geometry classification)
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HBIM	Historic Building Information Modelling
HSV	Hue Saturation Value (color model)
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISPRS	International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing
IST	Instituto Superior Técnico (Lisbon Portugal)
JPG	Image format (JPEG)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KNN	k-Nearest Neighbours
LLM	Large Language Model
LOA	Level of Accuracy
LOD	Level of Development / Detail
LOG	Level of Geometry
LOH	Level of History
LOI	Level of Information
LOIN	Level of Information Need

LOK	Level of Knowledge
LOQ	Level of Quality
MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
MIDP	Master Information Delivery Plan
ML	Machine Learning
MLS	Mobile Laser Scanning
MPDT	Model Production Delivery Table
NER	Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines
NURBS	Named Entity Recognition
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
QBM (VRI)	Quantitative Building Measurement (Visual Roughness Index)
SAM	Segment Anything Model
SfM	Structure from Motion
TLS	Terrestrial Laser Scanning
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
VPL	Visual Programming Language
VPLs	Visual Programming Languages
VR	Virtual Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

HBIM (Heritage/Historic Building Information Modelling) is garnering significant attention in the AEC industry, primarily due to its vital contribution to the preservation of historical and cultural heritage (Lovell et al., 2023a; Zhuo et al., 2024). HBIM is the digital modelling and management of historic buildings using BIM technologies for the preservation, analysis, and effective management of cultural heritage sites (Arayici et al., 2017; Lovell et al., 2023a). This is a relatively new field (López et al., 2018a), as BIM technology was originally intended for new construction (Volk et al., 2014), and due to the lack of tools for digitising existing buildings, the process was usually quite laborious and manual Croce et al., (2023).

As AI continues to gain momentum, automation is increasingly recognized as a fundamental component of workflows in the AEC sector (Wuni and Shen, 2019), including within the domain of HBIM. In response, various scholars have proposed automated or semi-automated approaches to address this complex process (Campagnolo et al., 2023; Güneş et al., 2024; LUÍS PEDRO NEVES SANHUDO, n.d.), which involves a large number of difficulties in the digitalisation process, ranging from the complexity of the geometric and non-standard/irregular shapes of the digitized objects (objects under study) to the analysis and semantic content of the BIM model, given the limited sources and, in general, the data that can be obtained if the data has not been documented (which is rather unrealistic).

1.2 Problem Statement

Currently, fully automated processes for the segmentation of historical buildings within the HBIM framework already exist, such as those proposed by Campagnolo et al., (2023). However, these methods are typically limited to coarse classification of elements into general categories (walls, columns, floors, etc.). While this approach is valuable for general modelling purposes, it can be insufficient when a high Level of Detail and Level of Information Need (LOD–LOIN) is required. For instance, in cases where it is necessary to predict the behaviour of each individual stone and to assign or integrate semantic data regarding completed or planned investigations, such as geological and petrographic analysis, ultrasonic testing, or QBM (VRI).

Some studies have attempted to address the limitations of coarse segmentation for historical brick masonry. For instance, Güneş et al., (2024) proposed a post-processing method for segmented point cloud data to semi-automatically detect individual building elements such as bricks in historical walls. This approach involves analysing neighbourhoods of points and classified areas to identify and correct misclassified points, thereby reducing segmentation errors and reconstructing bricks close to their original form. Nevertheless, despite its high efficiency, the method still requires manual refinement of the resulting data.

1.3 Research Gap

High-resolution segmentation plays a critical role in HBIM, particularly in the context of stone masonry. While most existing studies focus on coarse segmentation, identifying architectural components such as walls, doors, and windows. There is a noticeable lack of research dedicated to the detailed segmentation of individual stones. However, such granularity is essential for monitoring the condition of each stone element and for enabling subsequent structural analysis and validation. This lack of detailed stone-level segmentation methods constitutes a significant gap in current research.

1.4 Objectives

The focus of this research is the segmentation of Romanesque-period stone masonry, distinguished by its irregularly shaped stones. This research defines a set of AI and Photogrammetry tools aimed at automating Historic Building Classification and HBIM-based Modelling of historic buildings with stone masonry. On the basis of selected tools, research focuses on the automated generation of building components, including individual stone masonry elements, integrated with semantic data using the São João church as a case study object.

This study presents a facade analysis approach that draws conceptual inspiration from grammar-based parsing methods (Teboul et al., 2013), but it is implemented using segmentation with Convolutional neural networks, specifically U-Net and SAM. Unlike existing methods that focus on detecting general building categories (such as walls, windows, doors, etc.), the proposed approach emphasizes the segmentation of stone masonry and the identification of individual stone blocks as distinct entities. The resulting data can be utilized for high-detail 3D reconstruction and can be integrated into Historical Building Information Modelling (HBIM) systems. 2D masonry masks in the photos of the case study historical building are automatically generated by the SAM model. Masks include at least 3 classes: stone blocks, joints between stones, and the surroundings captured in photogrammetry images. Generated masks are raised in 3D, projecting them through COLMAP poses with multi-view voting to obtain a semantically and instantaneously marked point cloud ready for HBIM modelling.

1.5 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is structured into five chapters. The first chapter introduces the background of the study, outlines the research motivation and objectives, and defines the scope and methodological orientation. The second chapter reviews the existing body of literature, focusing on the concepts of Heritage BIM, the development of Scan-to-HBIM workflows, and the current state of automation in this field. It also identifies research gaps that frame the contribution of the present work. The third chapter presents the case study proposal, describing the chosen object of study, its historical and architectural context, the available survey data, and the applied methodological framework. The fourth chapter discusses the results of the case study, contextualizing the findings, interpreting their implications, and acknowledging the challenges and limitations encountered, while also outlining potential future directions. The final chapter concludes the thesis by synthesizing its main contributions, reflecting on the relevance of the adopted approach, and offering recommendations for further research and professional practice in the domain of Scan-to-HBIM and heritage documentation.

1.6 Main Findings

The conducted research has confirmed the feasibility of integrating artificial intelligence and photogrammetry into Scan-to-HBIM workflows, with emphasis placed on the detailed segmentation of Romanesque stone masonry. A methodological pipeline was developed that combined deep learning-based façade segmentation using U-Net and SAM with 3D projection through COLMAP, enabling the generation of semantically enriched point clouds suitable for incorporation into HBIM environments. The results demonstrated that convolutional neural networks are capable of classifying masonry components such as stone blocks, joints, and openings with relatively high accuracy in the recognition of primary elements, although challenges remain in the precise delineation of fine-grained stone boundaries. Segmentation performance was constrained by the limited size of the dataset, the quality of annotations, and the presence of photogrammetric noise. Nevertheless, the proposed workflow establishes a novel connection between 2D image segmentation and 3D semantic reconstruction, thereby providing a more efficient alternative to conventional manual practices. Although the achieved accuracy levels are not yet sufficient for direct implementation in conservation-oriented HBIM projects, the study provides a methodological baseline for automated stone-level modelling and demonstrates the potential of AI-driven approaches to advance from coarse architectural classification towards detailed and information-rich documentation of cultural heritage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Heritage BIM: Concepts, HBIM uses, Standardization Challenges

HBIM (Historic/Heritage Building Information Modeling) is an extension of BIM methodology adapted for the digital recording, analysis, and management of cultural heritage objects: starting with Murphy's definition (Murphy et al., 2009), where the process is based on the integration of laser scanning/photogrammetry and libraries of parametric objects, and the model serves as the basis for project documentation and research on existing structures. Recent reviews emphasize that HBIM is focused on typologically based modeling of elements (according to artistic, historical, and structural characteristics), consolidation of heterogeneous data, and support for conservation, while the automatic transformation of point clouds into BIM components remains limited. (López et al., 2018b) In applied restoration scenarios, HBIM allows several “slices” of history to be recorded — from interpretable periods to phases of restoration work — and relies on systematic “scan-to-HBIM” procedures (Moyano et al., 2022). However, this field still lacks standardization: there is a need for agreed information requirements (OIR/LOIN) and agreement on levels of detail/geometry (LOD/LOG), as confirmed by methodological and review work and research on automatic classification of geometry levels (Abualdenien and Borrmann, 2022a). Recent summary studies and initiatives propose structured HBIM standardization frameworks that integrate scan-to-BIM, LOA/LOD/LOI levels, and heritage preservation principles to make models reproducible and suitable for interagency use (Salah et al., 2025). The most common barriers are gaps in standards, insufficient automation, and a lack of tools for storing/sharing semantics for conservation practices, which is consistent with the mapping of HBIM challenges, gaps, and limitations (Lovell et al., 2023b).

HBIM uses

Throughout a building's life cycle, various tasks need to be addressed at each stage. To handle these tasks effectively, a Building Information Modeling (BIM) model is utilized. The structure and content of this model are determined by specific objectives, referred to as BIM uses. Unlike new construction, HBIM, an adaptation of BIM for historical/heritage buildings, possesses distinctive characteristics.

An insightful study on this subject is a paper published by Siewczyński and Jan Szot (2025). This research investigates various applications of HBIM, highlighting its objectives and BIM uses (Figure 1) throughout different stages of a historic building's life cycle by employing a methodology developed by the Pennsylvania State University (Figure 2).

Figure 1 – HBIM Uses and the HBIM Goals they support with an indication of which BIM perspective they refer to (Siewczyński and Jan Szot, 2025)

Plan	Design	Build	Operate
	2D to BIM / existing condition modeling		
	Scan2BIM / existing condition modeling		
	open standards		
	GIS integration		
Photo to BIM			
AI analyses			
Environmental analyses			
Lightning analyses			
BPS analyses			
FEM analyses			
VPL automation			
CIDOC integration			
Structural analyses			
Data standarization			
		CDE	
			AR/VR
			Facilty Management
			HBIM
			Multi-criteria analyses

Figure 2 - BIM Uses in identified cases of HBIM methodology implementation. (Siewczyński and Jan Szot, 2025)

Siewczyński and Jan Szot (2025) described the framework for HBIM implementation relating to BIM-related documents (Figure 3). The study shows that HBIM implementation complies with current BIM standards and document management regulations (including ISO 19650, PAS 1192, etc.), which allows it to be integrated into existing data management processes. At the same time, the creation of a cultural heritage object model is considered not only as the construction of three-dimensional geometry, but also as its inclusion in a formalised information management cycle: from defining customer requirements (EIR) to operation in a common data environment (CDE), which ensures reproducibility and consistency with generally accepted BIM processes.

Figure 3 – Connection of identified uses groups to documents prepared by appointing and appointed parties, including respectively EIR Exchange Information Requirement, MPDT Model Production Delivery Table, BEP BIM Execution Plan.

According to Kamaruzaman (2019a), the HBIM workflow consists of three main phases, namely Data Acquisition, Data Processing, and 3D Modelling (Figure 4). Regardless of which BIM uses HBIM model is selected, it all starts with existing condition capture, namely Data Acquisition. The Data acquisition phase is the initial stage and, therefore, decisive in the process of forming an HBIM model (Murphy et al., 2025).

Figure 4 – Workflow of HBIM (Kamaruzaman, 2019a)

Existing Conditions Capture - Data Acquisition techniques in HBIM

In modern practice, since the quality of subsequent modelling directly depends on the accuracy of the information obtained, two methods are most widely used for digital recording of heritage objects: digital photogrammetry and laser scanning. Both approaches have their advantages and limitations and are often used in combination, complementing each other. The article “Static Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) for Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM): A Systematic Review” (Liu et al., 2023) provides a systematic review of current research on the use of static terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) for modeling heritage buildings within the HBIM framework. Based on an analysis of 58 publications from 2012–2022 selected via the PRISMA protocol, the authors summarize the main TLS applications: high-precision geometric documentation, 3D modeling, and data integration into HBIM. The main TLS applications and the process of HBIM model development are illustrated in Figure 5. Overall, the study highlights that TLS delivers exceptional accuracy and reliability, yet the field lacks standardized survey guidelines and automated tools for converting point clouds into parametric BIM objects. It also notes the underutilized potential of TLS for long-term structural monitoring of heritage sites (Liu et al., 2023).

Figure 5 – Data Acquisition techniques in HBIM (Liu et al., 2023)

The accuracy of point cloud acquisition is of fundamental importance for HBIM development, since geometric inconsistencies at the survey stage inevitably propagate into the modelling phase and may compromise both dimensional reliability and the semantic structuring of the model (Brumana et al., 2018; Matrone et al., 2020). Abreu et al. (2023) indicated factors influencing a TLS measurement (Figure 6). As highlighted in systematic reviews, factors such as scanner calibration, scanning geometry, surface reflectivity, and environmental conditions directly affect the density and precision of acquired datasets (Liu et al., 2023). Limitations in TLS (Figure 7), including range dependency, colour distortions, and difficulties in capturing occluded areas, not only slow down the modelling process but also result in incomplete or biased representations of heritage structures (Liu et al., 2023; Valero et al., 2018). In HBIM applications, these deficiencies can lead to misinterpretations of historical construction techniques, loss of detail in masonry analysis, and reduced interoperability when models are used for conservation decision-making (Riveiro et al., 2016; Penjor et al., 2024).

Figure 6 - Factors influencing a TLS measurement (Abreu et al., 2023).

Category	Limitations or Challenges of TLS
Data Acquisition	Limited range of TLS: most roofs and upper building facades were out of range of TLS. Other RC technologies, such as UAVs, had to be used to compensate.
	Poor results of capturing colors with the camera mounted on the scanner in varying lighting conditions are due to time gaps between the successive scans.
	The distance from the scanner to the scanned object greatly influences the quality of the captured point cloud.
	Scanners were used in dangerous areas.
	Maintain the stability of the scaffolding that was set up for scanning.
	It is impossible to perform a static laser scanning acquisition in some areas due to safety issues. Therefore, a handheld Mobile Mapping System (MMS) was used to capture those areas.
	Lack of capability to capture images using the scanner.
Data Processing	Had to dismantle the building to scan the bracket set with hidden geometry.
	Combine multiple point cloud datasets created from different approaches (e.g., TLS and aerial photogrammetry) into one single point cloud.
	Number of software applications required to process the scan data
	Processing TLS scans is time-consuming.
	Incorporation of TLS scans from two separate campaigns that were 10 years apart.

Figure 7 - Limitations and challenges adapted from (Liu et al., 2023)

Data Processing

The next stage of DATA processing involves converting the raw data obtained during the DATA acquisition stage into a 3D HBIM model by segmenting building elements and integrating semantic alphanumeric data (Matrone et al., 2023). Already at the stage of segmenting the geometry of a historic building, it becomes necessary to choose the most optimal approach to segmentation by manually separating elements or by automatic or semi-automatic segmentation. At this stage, LOD/LOIN plays a key role, since, depending on BIM uses, requirements have already been drawn up for the level of detail of the geometry, as well as the semantic/informational component of the HBIM model required for this project. The development of HBIM is based on adapting the Level of Development (LOD) standards developed for modern construction to the specifics of cultural heritage sites. Classic LOD scales (100 - 600 or 0-4) are used to determine the level of geometric and informational detail. For example, Brumana et al. (2021) describe the use of LOD and LOG (Level of Geometry) for modeling monastery vaults and masonry. Various systems are encountered in research, and it is notable that they are influenced by Regional peculiarities.

Table 1 - National standards and local practices applied for HBIM in varied countries

Italy	United States	Spain	Canada	Argentina
UNI 11337:2017	AIA standards	LOK concept (Level of Knowledge)	LOD-LOI-LOA system	LOD 100-500 and A-G scale
LOD is integrated into restoration projects (e.g., the Basilica of Collemaggio and the Church of San Lorenzo).	application of AIA standards, supplemented by Heritage Scotland requirements, for working with historic ships and administrative buildings (Liu et al., 2023).	development of the LOK concept for conservation and restoration planning strategies Castellano-Román and Puerto (2019)	Multi-level systems include LOD-LOI-LOA for modeling Parliament Hill buildings, allowing for consideration of not only geometry but also data accuracy (Graham et al., 2018). Chow et al. (2019)	Alternative standards application which is a mixed model (LOD 100-500 and A-G scale) for the restoration of historic districts (Moreira et al., 2018).

Thus, it can be stated that at the current stage, LOD/LOIN approaches are fragmented, and there is no international standard, which leads to difficulties in data integration and exchange. As discussed by Abualdenien and Borrmann (2022b), the Level of Development (LOD) comprises two complementary components: geometric representation (LOG) and semantic information (LOI). Within the standard BIM approach, levels of detail (LOD) and levels of information (LOIN) are somehow regulated by normative documentation, which is updated annually.

LOD in HBIM

While LOD is a well-established concept in traditional BIM, its application in HBIM requires adaptation due to the irregular and complicated geometries that characterize historical buildings. Unlike modern structures, which often consist of standardized elements, heritage buildings present a range of complex architectural features that demand higher customization and detail. Therefore, determining the LOD is essential for as-built BIM, as it impacts model effects and modeling efforts (Sun et al., 2019). In HBIM, the Level of Detail (LOD) defines the degree of geometric precision and complexity of a digital model, requiring adaptation due to the irregular and unique geometries of historical buildings, unlike the standardized elements of modern architecture (Chourasia et al., 2019). At lower levels, models rely on simplified forms such as walls, roofs, and floors, which are sufficient for inventories or early restoration planning. Higher LODs capture detailed features such as masonry, carvings, and decorative elements, demanding advanced surveying methods like laser scanning and photogrammetry (Lin et al., 2024).

Several scholars emphasize the critical role of LOD selection: Brumana et al. (2019) link it to the accurate representation and conservation of heritage features. Brusaporci et al. (2018) discuss the challenges of aligning heritage documentation with conventional LOD standards, and Chow et al. (2020) propose tailored LOD definitions for historic contexts. Biljecki et al. (2016) proposed an extended set of 16 LODs based on façade geometry grades, emphasizing their relevance for historic building documentation.

Figure 8 - 16 LODs based on façade geometry grades. Adapted from (Biljecki et al., 2016)

In contrast to traditional BIM, LOD in HBIM lacks a universally accepted methodology. The complexity and uniqueness of heritage geometries require a project-specific approach to defining the appropriate level of detail. Consequently, LOD in HBIM functions more as a flexible guideline than a fixed scale, with its definition depending on project objectives and the cultural value of the asset.

In this context, the concept of LOIN (Level of Information Need), first formalized in ISO 19650-1:2018, is gaining increasing importance. LOIN integrates both geometric (LOD) and informational (LOI) aspects, enabling the adaptation of model detail to heritage-specific requirements. For HBIM, this shift is particularly relevant, as it ensures that not only the physical form but also the historical, cultural, and material dimensions of heritage assets are adequately represented. Thus, moving towards LOIN provides a more comprehensive framework, overcoming the limitations of traditional LOD standards in heritage documentation and conservation.

LOD in HBIM. Defines the semantic depth of the model by integrating material characteristics, historical context, and conservation data. In HBIM, LOI ensures that heritage assets are documented not only as geometric forms but also as culturally significant entities enriched with descriptive knowledge.

LOA (Level of Accuracy). Refers to the precision of the geometric representation and the tolerance between the digital model and the physical structure. For HBIM, LOA is critical, as even minor deviations can compromise authenticity in restoration and conservation workflows.

LOK (Level of Knowledge). Captures the cumulative knowledge embedded in the model, enabling dynamic updates as new archaeological or historical findings emerge. This transforms HBIM from a static repository into an evolving knowledge system that reflects the growing understanding of heritage assets.

LOQ (Level of Quality). Concerns the reliability and credibility of the data sources used to construct the model. Within HBIM, LOQ assures stakeholders that the digital model provides a trustworthy foundation for preservation, decision-making, and long-term cultural management.

The combined application of LOI, LOA, LOK, and LOQ creates a multidimensional HBIM framework that extends beyond conventional LOD-based approaches. This integration guarantees not only the geometric accuracy of digital heritage models but also their semantic richness, historical depth, knowledge adaptability, and data reliability. Such a holistic framework is vital for cultural heritage, ensuring that HBIM models function as accurate, meaningful, and enduring tools for conservation, restoration, and heritage management (Salah et al., 2025).

An essential aspect in the development of HBIM models is the logical organization of the database, which ensures both the systematic structuring and long-term usability of information. As emphasized by De Falco et al. (2024), the organization of data relies on indexing elements according to hierarchical levels such as floor, room, and individual unit, while also associating them with technical and descriptive attributes as well as diagnostic results. The example of such a hierarchy is shown in Figure 9. This approach enables the model to function not only as a geometric representation but also as a repository of heterogeneous information, integrating survey data with material analyses and historical records.

In the context of stone masonry segmentation and further HBIM creation, the logical organization of the database is of particular importance, since the segmentation of masonry and architectural components through AI methods produces a large number of discrete elements. Without a coherent parameterization and indexing system, these segmented entities risk remaining as isolated geometries with limited analytical value. A structured database organization ensures that each stone, window, or door is not only spatially referenced but also enriched with identifiers and relevant semantic attributes. This, in turn, enhances the interoperability of the HBIM model, facilitates cross-disciplinary collaboration, and

strengthens its role as a decision-support tool for conservation and restoration practices.

Figure 9 - Logical organization of the database. Adapted from (De Falco et al., 2024)

2.2 Existing Scan-to-HBIM Workflows

The article by López et al. (2018a) provide an overview of existing approaches to HBIM aimed at documenting, virtually restoring, and managing cultural heritage sites. It is noted that standard BIM platforms such as Autodesk Revit and Graphisoft Archicad, originally designed for new buildings with simple shapes, are not always suitable for complex historical structures. To solve this problem, a semi-automatic workflow is used: specialists create parametric objects using a combination of sections, shapes (NURBS, B-Rep), and historical documentation, and then form HBIM libraries adapted to architectural styles and heritage elements. Point clouds serve as input material for building components directly on them, without losing details; regular surfaces are implemented through standard BIM elements, and irregularly structured ones through B-Rep. The described approaches are illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Diagram describing the manual construction method of HBIM library(López et al., 2018a).

Malinverni et al., (2019a) examined an example of HBIM application for documenting the condition and degradation of materials at the Chiesa della Pietà cultural heritage site in Fermo (Figure 11). The authors proposed a process based on a combination of laser scanning data and historical documentation, which allowed them to manually reconstruct architectural elements and link them to semantic information through thematic mapping. Levels of detail (LOD) and a system of identification codes were implemented in the model to track the various stages of deterioration. This approach demonstrated the potential of HBIM as a tool for managing cultural heritage preservation, but it remains labour-intensive and requires significant manual effort. A limitation of the method is the lack of automation, which makes it unsuitable for large-scale projects and highlights the need for the development of semi-automated and intelligent approaches in the field of Scan-to-HBIM.

DECAY	DESCRIPTION	CAUSES
	SURFACE DEPOSIT NATURAL MODIFICATION OF THE SURFACE NOT CONNECTABLE TO DECAY PHENOMENA AND PERCEPTIBLE AS A VARIATION OF THE NATURAL COLOR	-MECHANICAL EROSION OF RAIN -WIND EROSION -CHEMICAL AGGRESSION FROM POLLUTANTS -FORMATION OF ICE ON THE SURFACE
	LAITENCE FORMATION OF SUBSTANCE ON THE SURFACE OF THE BUILDING WITH WHITISH COLOR OF CRYSTALLINE, DUSTED AND FILAMENTOUS APPEARANCE	-MECHANICAL EROSION OF RAIN
	BIOLOGICAL PATINA COLOR LAYER SEES THIN, SOFT AND HOMOGENEOUS, ADHERENT TO THE SURFACE AND OF EVIDENT BIOLOGICAL NATURE	-ACCUMULATIONS OF MOISTURE -ATTACK OF AUTOTROPHIC ORGANISMS (BACTERIA, UNICELLULARS, LICHENS, FUNGUS)
	SURFACE WASHOUT VARIATION OF ONE OR MORE PARAMETERS THAT DEFINE THE COLOR. IN THIS CASE IT MANIFESTS ITSELF IN THE FORM OF A LARGE DISCOLORATION ON THE BUILDING	-RAINWATER RUNOFF
	DISINTEGRATION OF MALTA JOINTS DE-COHESION CHARACTERIZED BY THE DETACHMENT OF GRANULES OR CRYSTALS FROM MORTAR STRATIGRAPHY	-MECHANICAL EROSION OF RAIN -WIND EROSION -CHEMICAL AGGRESSION FROM POLLUTANTS -FORMATION OF ICE ON THE SURFACE
	STAIN LOCALIZED CHROMATIC VARIATION OF THE SURFACE, CORRELATED TO THE PRESENCE OF FOREIGN MATERIALS (WATER, OXIDATION PRODUCTS, PAINTS, ORGANIC SUBSTANCES)	-INFILTRATION HUMIDITY
	LEAKAGE DARK STAINS WITH A VERTICAL COURSE BELOW THE PROJECTIONS	-RAINWATER RUNOFF
	ABSENCE FALL OR LOSS OF PARTS OF MATERIAL	-MECHANICAL EROSION BY ATMOSPHERIC AGENTS
	CONCRETION COMPACT DEPOSIT GENERALLY FORMED BY ELEMENTS OF LIMITED EXTENSION, DEVELOPED PREFERENTIALLY IN A SINGLE DIRECTION NOT COINCIDING WITH THE STONE SURFACE	-MECHANICAL EROSION OF RAIN -ACCUMULATIONS OF MOISTURE
	INCONGRUABLE PATCH ANTHROPIC INTERVENTION ON THE SURFACE OF THE BUILDING THAT AESTHETICALLY DETERIORATES THE BUILDING ITSELF	-ANTHROPIC INTERVENTION
	INCONGRUOUS ELEMENTS PRESENCE OF INCONGRUOUS ELEMENTS THAT AESTHETICALLY DETERIORATE THE SURFACE OF THE BUILDING	-ANTHROPIC INTERVENTION

Figure 11 - Example of thematic map of the material decay and related descriptive legend (Malinverni et al., 2019a)

Penjor et al., (2024) identified the principal challenges and limitations of HBIM in cultural heritage preservation, highlighting several critical barriers. These include technical difficulties in capturing complex or damaged architectural geometries with laser scanning and photogrammetry, the high dependence on qualified interdisciplinary experts, and limited accuracy in reproducing historical details for degraded structures. Furthermore, integration issues with other digital platforms such as GIS, VR, or digital twins, along with the absence of standardized guidelines and protocols, significantly constrain the effective and widespread implementation of HBIM in heritage management technology and require further research and development of specialised solutions.

Examples of automation in stone and brick masonry segmentation. Limitations and comparisons.

In recent years, several different approaches to masonry segmentation have been proposed in HBIM and architectural heritage research. One notable example of full automation in this area is the original method proposed by Valero et al. (2018), where the automatic segmentation of point clouds of rubble walls were obtained by using TLS (Terrestrial Laser Scanning), which allowed the separation of individual stone blocks and mortar areas. Using both geometric and colour data, the authors applied a 2D wavelet transform (CWT) to identify the boundaries between stones and joints, without requiring the wall surface to be flat or vertical, which is important for historical objects with deformations. The method was tested on examples of significant architectural objects from Scotland, and it demonstrated the ability to automatically measure the depth of mortar and the position of stones, which significantly improves the efficiency and accuracy of surveying and analysis for restoration and maintenance tasks. This approach is a striking example of rule-based automation, in which segmentation is performed entirely algorithmically, reducing the subjectivity and speed of traditional surveys. However, it is limited in its flexibility: it works well on TLS data but does not translate well to noisier and less detailed photogrammetric point clouds. Although feasible for application to the case study building, namely the São João de Calvos church, adapting this method would entail an excessive and impractical workload.

Another strategy where each brick was modelled as a separate element was demonstrated by Brumana.R et al., (2018). The authors of this work actually developed an HBIM library of bricks and arches, which made it possible to reproduce the logic of stereotomy and the construction techniques of historical masters. The source data was a point cloud obtained using TLS and photogrammetry, which provided high-precision geometry of the arches. Based on these, the bricks were arranged in a parametric HBIM environment (LOD 500), where some of the elements were formed directly from the cloud (GOG 9), and some through typological reconstruction based on construction rules and historical repertoires (GOG 10). This process involves the automation of only the stages of shooting and obtaining point clouds, while the modelling of individual bricks and their location required expert interpretation. From a technical point of view, this ensured millimetre accuracy in the representation of the masonry, allowed for the analysis of geometric deformations of the arches and their structural stability, and created the basis for the formation of a library of parametric elements that can be used in further HBIM projects for the reproducible modelling of complex historical masonry (Brumana et al., 2018). Despite the high accuracy demonstrated by the final HBIM model, this method is labour-intensive and dependent on expert interpretation, which limits its scalability to large data sets.

A completely different approach was adopted in the study by Güneş et al., (2024), which proposed a method for semi-automated reconstruction of brick walls based on segmented point clouds. The authors rely on deep learning methods for automatic segmentation, but note that unique architectural features and degradation of historical surfaces often lead to local classification errors. To eliminate them, a post-processing algorithm has been developed that uses analysis of local point neighbourhoods and segmented areas to identify anomalies and correct incorrect labels. This combination of automatic segmentation based on neural network models and intelligent semi-automatic post-processing significantly reduces the error rate and provides a more accurate reconstruction of the masonry, close to its original form, thereby increasing the reliability of the digital representation of historical structures. However, it also demonstrates dependence on manual labelling for training and difficulty in adapting to

new datasets.

Table 2 - Comparative analysis of masonry morphological characteristics and segmentation methods in similar case studies

Main Characteristics	Konya Sahip Ata Hanikah (brick)	Magio Grasselli palace in Cremona (brick)	São João de Calvos church (stone)	Craigmillar Castle/ Linlithgow Palace (rubble masonry)
Segmentation type	Semi-automated	Manual / rule-based modeling	Semi-automated	Automatic (rule-based, CWT)
Size	Relatively consistent	Relatively consistent, varies by vault zone	Highly variable	Highly variable non-uniform
Shape	Nearly rectangular	Irregular, curved, non-rectangular	Often irregular, wedge-shaped	Irregular, joints can be very narrow and boundaries blurred;
Laying technique	Uniform and orderly	Bricks laid: in folio (flat tiles), soldier courses, diagonal/herringbone patterns, parallel to springers, cone-shaped at corners.	Irregular, with large joints	Irregular, 'random' laying; stones laid without strict orientation, joint thickness varies
Shape origin	Manually molded brick	Cut/modeled by stereotomic rules	Hewn or unprocessed natural stone	Natural stone (natural rubble) roughly processed or completely unprocessed
Segmentation difficulty	Lower	Lower	Moderate complexity	High (higher)
Tools applied along with pointcloud data	k-NN	thermography, HBIM modeling	UNet/SAM	Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT)
Visual representation	 (Valero et al., 2018)			

A comparison of these three approaches shows that there is currently no universal and fully automated solution for masonry segmentation: rule-based methods are too narrowly specialized and poorly

adaptable to new data, while supervised approaches require large amounts of annotated data. It is also worth noting that the CWT method is the most suitable for the object under study.

After analysing existing approaches to the segmentation of stone and brick masonry, identifying their characteristics and applicability to the segmentation of Romanesque masonry, it was decided to use a combination of U-Net (for semantic segmentation on facade images where mask annotation is available) and SAM+COLMAP (for adaptive segmentation and retraining without huge datasets). This choice allows us to combine the strengths of CNN architectures (robustness and accuracy on limited data) and foundation models (flexibility and portability), providing a more reproducible and scalable pipeline for masonry segmentation in the context of HBIM.

2.3 Automation in Scan-to-HBIM: Strategies and Techniques

Figure 12 - Different types of Machine Learning systems Adapted from (Battini et al., 2024)

Semi-automated approaches

Chelaru et al. (2024) present an integrated workflow within HBIM that combines point clouds, archive data, and building condition survey results. Standard BIM environments were used to process the geometry, primarily Autodesk Revit (with the ReCap module for importing and registering point clouds), as well as specialised plugins and tools such as CloudCompare for pre-processing scans and

aligning data. The article pays particular attention to the standardisation of data and processes, which is considered a key condition for the integration of heterogeneous sources. The authors emphasize the importance of using IFC (openBIM) as a universal format for exchange, as well as formalized BIM regulation documents (e.g., EIR, BEP, CDE), which make the process reproducible and consistent between different project participants. This approach not only consolidates the geometry, but also links the HBIM model to historical, archival, and diagnostic materials, which increases its value for decision-making in restoration. A similar semi-automated rule-based approach could be applied in the current work by automating the stages of shooting and pre-processing point clouds (registration, filtering, basic geometric segmentation), integrating archival materials through Revit/IFC, and then manually supplementing the model with semantics (for example, highlighting individual masonry stones or their condition). This combination of routine automation and expert interpretation will increase the efficiency of HBIM model construction and maintain a high level of detail in the analysis.

Croce et al., (2023) presented a semi-automatic Scan-to-BIM approach for cultural heritage sites based on semantic segmentation of point clouds using the Random Forest algorithm. The authors tested the method on laser and photogrammetric data of monastery cloisters in Tuscany (Italy), classifying architectural elements (walls, columns, arches, vaults, etc.). The segmented data was integrated into the HBIM environment, where BIM models were reconstructed using template geometries and visual programming (VPL). The approach reduces the labour intensity of manual marking and increases the reproducibility of the process of documenting and analysing architectural heritage.

Matrone et al., (2020) presented the ArCH benchmark dataset, which contains labelled point clouds of historical buildings (TLS and photogrammetry), classified by architectural elements (walls, roofs, windows, doors, columns, arches, etc.). The work falls under the category of supervised learning, as the dataset is intended for training and testing semantic segmentation algorithms. The authors demonstrated the application of popular models (PointNet, PointNet++, DGCNN) and evaluated their accuracy using IoU, Accuracy, and F1-score metrics. Here, IoU (Intersection over Union) represents a standard metric in semantic segmentation that measures the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, calculated as the ratio of their intersection to their union. The main contribution of the study is the creation of a standardised database that provides an objective comparison of methods and serves as a basis for the development of automation in the field of Scan-to-HBIM and cultural heritage analysis.

Haznedar et al.,(2023) applied supervised learning with PointNet architecture to the task of semantic segmentation of point clouds of historical objects (Gaziantep, Turkey), classifying structures into walls, roofs, floors, doors, and windows. A manually labelled dataset of 28 buildings was used, which was divided into training (~70–80%) and test (~20–30%) samples. The study showed that segmentation accuracy improves significantly when trained on synthetic (restitution-based) data suitable for heritage architecture. The level of automation of the methodology is partial automation, since segmentation is performed automatically, while data annotation remains manual.

Moyano et al., (2024) compare the effectiveness of various machine learning and deep learning methods for segmenting point clouds of cultural and historical structures within HBIM. Their study tests

classification algorithms, including Random Forest, classic geomatics tools (commercial software solutions), and a variant of the PointNet architecture (neural network). The authors show that all of the approaches listed - both traditional and deep - are capable of performing segmentation effectively, with the accuracy of the models being evaluated by HBIM experts. The work highlights the potential of AI in simplifying and accelerating reverse modelling procedures for complex historical forms and structures.

Table 3 – Semi-Automated Scan to HBIM

Authors	Algorithms	Tasks	Dataset/ Data type	Study Focus
Rule-based automation				
(Güneş et al., 2024) Mustafa C. Güneş; A. Mertan; Y. H. Sahin; G. Unal; M. Özkar	Semi-automated post-processing method applied to already segmented point clouds; correction of misclassified regions (bricks vs mortar) without training a new ML model	Minimization of segmentation errors in brick–mortar structures of historic masonry walls; detecting misclassified points and refining brick geometry for more accurate reconstruction	Segmented point clouds of historic masonry walls; classes include bricks and mortar	Improvement of HBIM segmentation accuracy in masonry structures, ensuring more reliable brick-by-brick modeling from point clouds
K. Pavelka Jr.	TLS (Leica BLK360), mobile laser scanning (ZEB-REVO), photogrammetry (drone and terrestrial) with processing in Agisoft Metashape, RealityCapture, and CloudCompare for generating point clouds, orthophotos, and photo-plans	Documentation and diagnostics of a damaged historic minaret; creation of dense point clouds, orthophotos, façade photo-plans, and a base HBIM model	Proprietary dataset: TLS (13 stations), mobile scanning, UAV imagery; data types include dense point clouds (textured/non-textured), orthophotos, and façade photo-plans; no semantic classes, only division into constructive parts (lower/middle/up per sections)	Automation of point cloud capture and processing; manual intervention required for segmentation of building parts and HBIM model construction
(Chelaru et al., 2024) C. Chelaru; M. Di Giuda; F. Villa;	Integration of point clouds, archival documentation,	Creation of an integrated HBIM model: combining geometric data	Point clouds (TLS/photogrammetry); archival sources	Demonstrate how integrating diverse data sources into HBIM can

L. Landi; S. Barazzetti	and condition assessment data into HBIM; automated processing of point clouds and data linking via HBIM tools.	(point cloud), semantic information from archives, and diagnostic data on damage; providing a basis for conservation and restoration.	(drawings, historical documentation); survey results (condition of materials, damage).	improve the accuracy and usefulness of models for heritage conservation and management.
Sithole (2008)	Weighted proximity segmentation + triangulated mesh	Brick detection in masonry walls	TLS point clouds + triangulated mesh. Classes: bricks vs. joints	Identifying bricks based on mortar channel depth and width
Supervised Machine Learning Approach				
(Haznedar et al., 2023) B. Haznedar; R. Bayraktar; A. E. Ozturk; Y. Arayici	deep neural network: implementation of PointNet for semantic segmentation of point clouds using labeled data	Semantic segmentation and classification of architectural elements	Dataset of 28 heritage buildings in Gaziantep (Turkey), laser-scanned point clouds labeled manually into five classes: walls, roofs, floors, doors, windows.	Partial automation – model predicts segmentation automatically; but dataset labelling is manual, and there is no automation of data acquisition or annotation
(Matrone et al., 2020) F. Matrone; A. Lingua; R. Pierdicca; E. S. Malinvernì; M. Paolanti; E. Grilli; F. Remondino; A. Murtiyoso; T. Landes	Creation of a benchmark with millions of manually labelled 3D points; use of ready-made DNN models (PointNet, PointNet++, DGCNN, etc.)	Semantic classification of cloud points with the ability to evaluate accuracy (Accuracy, F1-score, IoU)	ArCH dataset: 17 labelled and 10 unlabelled high-resolution point clouds (TLS + photogrammetry), 9 classes of architectural elements	Provide a reliable benchmark for the development, training and comparison of ML and DL models for the semantic segmentation of point clouds
V. Croce; G. Caroti; A. Piemonte; L. De Luca; P. Véron	Random Forest (RF) classifier for semantic segmentation of point clouds	Semi-automatic Scan-to-BIM reconstruction via propagation of template geometries using VPLs	Point clouds (LS and photogrammetry) of Tuscan cloisters; 9–10 classes (columns, arches, vaults, walls, floors, etc.)	ML classification with template-based BIM reconstruction via VPL

(Moyano et al., 2024) J. Moyano; A. Musicco; J. E. Nieto-Julián; J. P. Domínguez-Morales	Comparison of ML and DL Random Forest, commercial classification tools and PointNet-based neural network	Semantic segmentation of point clouds, highlighting architectural elements or surfaces based on geometric characteristics	Classes: architectural and structural units segmentation is based on geometry	Applicability and effectiveness assessment of ML and DL for segmenting complex architectural geometry.
Oses et al. (2014)	KNN, SVM, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree	Wall-level classification by masonry typology (not individual stones)	Photographic images of masonry typologies (coursed, uncoursed, ashlar, etc.)	Automatic classification of walls based on masonry assembly
(Malinverni et al., 2019b) Malinverni, Pierdicca, Paolanti, Martini, Morbidoni, Matrone & Lingua (2019)	PointNet++	Semantic segmentation of 3D point clouds into architectural element categories (e.g., walls, doors, columns, stairs)	Manually annotated LiDAR / TLS point clouds (XYZ plus optional features: RGB, normals, reflectance) Classes: architectural categories (9 defined classes + "other")	Automating semantic labelling of heritage point cloud data using DL, including dataset creation and release, performance evaluation, and full pipeline design
Unsupervised Machine Learning Approach				
Yue et al. (2003)	Thresholding + contour detection: region-based & edge-based	(Yue et al., 2003) Segmentation of material samples	Digital images of cylindrical concrete samples Classes: aggregates vs. binder	Segmentation of the internal structure of materials

An analysis of the publications included in Table 3 shows that semi-automated approaches in Scan-to-HBIM are used where fully automatic segmentation is either insufficiently reliable or requires expert correction. Rule-based methods (Chelaru et al., 2024; George Sithole, 2008; Güneş et al., 2024; Pavelka Jr., 2022) make a significant contribution to the pre-processing and post-correction of point clouds, ensuring consistent quality, but require manual interpretation in the final stages. Supervised ML approaches (Haznedar et al., 2023; Matrone et al., 2020; Croce et al.; Moyano et al., 2024; Malinverni et al., 2019) allow for high-precision segmentation of architectural elements, but still depend on manual annotation of large datasets. Unsupervised methods (Yue et al., 2003) are mainly used in laboratory

conditions and do not yet provide sufficient semantic accuracy for complex HBIM. Thus, semi-automated approaches offer a compromise between automation and quality control: they reduce labour costs but leave a key role to the expert, which makes them applicable in real projects but limits their scalability.

Campagnolo et al., (2023) proposed a fully automated Scan-to-BIM workflow based on deep learning methods for point cloud segmentation. The developed BIM-Net and BIM-Net++ architectures perform point-by-point semantic and instance segmentation, which allows for the identification and classification of building elements (walls, windows, doors, roofs, etc.) and the automatic reconstruction of a BIM model. The HePIC dataset, which includes annotated point clouds of historical buildings (~8.9 million points), was created for training and evaluating algorithms. Experiments have shown that BIM-Net++ outperforms existing state-of-the-art models (e.g., RandLA-Net and Cylinder3D) in terms of IoU and mIoU metrics.(Campagnolo et al., 2023)

For HBIM tasks and the documentation of historical structures, this study is important in that it demonstrates the possibility of automating the process of segmenting architectural elements from point clouds, reducing dependence on manual marking. This approach can also be applied to the analysis of masonry, where high-precision classification of building components of facades is required for subsequent integration into HBIM.

Teboul et al., (2013) developed a fully automatic method for parsing facades based on shape grammars and reinforcement learning (Figure 13). The approach combines architectural composition rules (facade grammar) with example-based learning, where an agent uses RL (reinforcement learning) to learn how to apply grammatical rules step by step to break down a facade into structural elements (windows, doors, floors). The Teboul et al. method is associated with high-level semantics and could potentially be used for stone segmentation approaches by using a structural, object-oriented representation, which could use “grammar-like constraints”. For instance, check the location of stones, correct errors by removing ‘impossible’ stone shapes, smooth the grid, and fix an erroneous hole in the wall.

Figure 13 - The colors of the segmentation indicate the different classes. Adapted from (Teboul et al., 2013)

Musicco et al., (2021) presented a fully automated unsupervised approach to diagnosing surface damage on historic buildings using colour clustering in HSV space and hierarchical clustering (Figure 14-15). This method allows for the identification of defects such as biopatin, coloured changes, stains and efflorescence, and links them to architectural elements through geometric segmentation. The method is applicable for analysing masonry, where it helps to automatically distinguish between stone and mortar, as well as to identify areas of surface damage, making it a valuable element in HBIM processes.

Figure 14 - Methodological Workflow, which combines Colour-based segmentation and Geometry-based segmentation. Adapted from (Musicco et al., 2021)

Figure 15 - From left to right: biological colonization and unaltered surface of the wall on the left; biological colonization and moist area of the wall visible on the right. Adapted from (Musicco et al., 2021)

Table 4 – Fully Automated Scan to HBIM

Authors	Algorithms	Tasks	Dataset/Data type	Study Focus
Supervised Machine Learning Approach				
(Battini et al., 2024) C. Battini; U. Ferretti; G. Angelis; M. Pierdicca; R. Paolanti; R. Quattrini	Shape grammar in the procedural generation of synthetic point clouds. Training is performed using deep networks, such as the improved DGCNN — RadDGCNN, in synthetic data conditions.	Semantic segmentation of historical elements (in particular, types of arches) in point clouds. The model recognises the type of arch based on its shape and structure.	Synthetically generated point clouds of marked vaults. Classes include: various vault types A total of ~6 marked models.	Validity of using synthetic data to train DL models for the segmentation of real data (TLS) of historical buildings. Demonstration of the effectiveness of the approach by overcoming the shortage of large labelled datasets.
(Campagnolo et al., 2023) D. Campagnolo; E. Camuffo; U. Michieli; P. Borin; S. Milani; A. Giordano	BIM-Net BIM-Net++	Point-wise semantic segmentation, Instance segmentation, Reconstruction of BIM objects	HePIC dataset 8 classes	End-to-end Scan-to-BIM pipeline minimizing human annotation; using few-shot learning strategies; outperforming other segmentation models on HePIC
(Teboul et al., 2013) O. Teboul; I. Kokkinos; L. Simon; P. Koutsourakis; N. Paragios	Shape Grammars + RL reinforcement learning	Segmentation of façade elements (windows, doors, columns, etc., via learned grammar-driven parsing policy	Facade images (2D or 3D representations) annotation with architectural components (e.g., windows, doors, columns).	RL-driven procedural grammar to interpret building façades, learning parsing policies that combine visual evidence and grammar rules. Aims to automate façade analysis with context-aware modeling.
Unsupervised Machine Learning Approach				

(Musicco et al., 2021) A. Musicco, R. A. Galantucci, S. Bruno, C. Verdoscia, F. Fatiguso	hierarchical clustering based on HSV colour data; geometry-based segmentation of 3D reconstructions	Clustering, feature extraction, anomaly detection	Photogrammetric point clouds of historical buildings; classes include types of surface alterations (colourimetric anomalies) and architectural components.	Detects decay phenomena in heritage masonry, leveraging both colour and geometry-based segmentation for diagnostic mapping
(Buldo et al., 2023) Buldo, Agustín-Hernández, Verdoscia & Tavolare (2023)	RANSAC model-fitting algorithms on point clouds	Automatic point cloud segmentation and parametric-adaptive modeling of vaulted systems within a Scan-to-BIM framework	Ideal user-defined models and LiDAR-acquired point clouds of masonry vaulted systems. Classes: semantic/structural and decorative elements (e.g., vault surfaces, architectural components)	Integrating segmentation and parametric modeling for HBIM-compatible 3D reconstruction of vaulted heritage structures
Rule-based automation				
(Riveiro et al., 2016)	(2.5D projection, filtering, Sobel gradients, geometry-constrained marker-controlled watershed)	Automatic segmentation of stones, detection of joints, morphological analysis (length, height, perimeter, area)	LiDAR point clouds (TLS & MLS) converted into 2.5D intensity images Classes: stone blocks, joints (mortar/dry)	Geometric segmentation of individual stones for structural evaluation
(Andriasyan et al., 2020) Andriasyan, Moyano, Nieto-Julián & Antón (2020)	geometric modeling via Marching Cubes, Delaunay triangulation, Ball-pivot, Volvox meshing; parametric object generation in Rhino+ Grasshopper to ArchiCAD	Automatic generation of textured 3D meshes and parametric BIM objects from point cloud data (Scan-to-HBIM)	TLS and SfM point clouds to textured meshes, then BIM parametric objects (Morph, mesh, GSM objects); no explicit semantic classes	Converting heritage point clouds into HBIM-compatible parametric models with embedded geometry and textures
(Escudero, 2023)	RANSAC for plane detection;	Converting a cloud to BIM with RGB and classification	TLS (E57) format converted to ASCII TXT	Creating a fully detailed, interoperable HBIM model enriched with

Dynamo scripting	Convert	TLS	Attributes: XYZ,	geometry, texture,
+	point cloud into		RGB, normals	and metadata for
Revit voxelization	detailed 3D BIM		Classes: color-	heritage
	model with color		based surfaces,	preservation and
	and metadata,		voxels	GIS integration
	export to IFC and			
	integrate to GIS			

A comparison of the studies presented in Table 4 shows that there is currently no single universal approach in the field of Scan-to-HBIM automation. Supervised deep learning (Battini et al., 2024; Campagnolo et al., 2023) demonstrates high accuracy in the semantic segmentation of architectural elements, but it depends on annotated datasets and requires significant computing resources. Reinforcement learning combined with shape grammars (Teboul et al., 2013) allows for context and architectural composition rules to be considered, but its practical application is limited by the complexity of training. Unsupervised methods (Musicco et al., 2021; Buldo et al., 2023) are attractive because they do not require manual annotation, but they are currently focused mainly on damage diagnosis and geometric modeling rather than full semantic reconstruction. At the same time, rule-based approaches (Riveiro et al., 2016; Andriasyan et al., 2020; Escudero, 2023) remain the most reproducible and applicable in practice, but require adaptation for each specific object and do not scale to different types of architecture.

Thus, the literature demonstrates a constant tension between the accuracy of supervised models and the versatility of unsupervised or rule-based solutions. This confirms the relevance of searching for hybrid approaches that would combine the semantic accuracy of DL networks with the flexibility of rule-based/unsupervised methods, as well as the possibility of using synthetic data for training when there is a lack of labelling.

Gaps and Challenges. Final review

A significant milestone in the development of Heritage BIM (HBIM) was the emergence of large-scale reference datasets specifically created for semantic segmentation of architectural point clouds. Matrone et al. (2020) presented the ArCH dataset (Figure 16), which includes both annotated and unannotated point clouds of cultural heritage objects obtained using laser scanning and photogrammetry. The dataset contains manual labelling of ten semantic classes, such as walls, floors, roofs, columns, arches, vaults, stairs, and decorative elements, thus providing a standardised basis for training and evaluating machine learning and deep learning algorithms. Unlike rule-based approaches or studies limited to individual cases, this benchmark allows for a systematic comparison of supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid methods, and guarantees the reproducibility of results in various architectural contexts. For research related to masonry segmentation and HBIM reconstruction, ArCH is a critical resource, providing both the scale and diversity of data needed to validate AI approaches and compare them with existing methodologies. (Matrone et al., 2020)

Figure 16 - ArCH dataset. Adapted from (Matrone et al., 2020)

The ArCH dataset is an important step for HBIM research, but it remains limited in scope. It mainly includes European heritage sites and ten broad semantic classes, making it insufficient to represent the full diversity of historical building typologies worldwide. Therefore, it should be seen as a specialized resource rather than a universal benchmark. Abreu et al., (2023) noted that a key limitation in the development of Scan-to-BIM and Scan-vs-BIM methods is the lack of representative benchmark datasets, especially for point clouds and photogrammetric data of different building typologies. Scan-to-BIM refers to the process of reconstructing BIM models from scan data, while Scan-vs-BIM methods focus on comparing reality capture (laser scans or photogrammetry) with BIM models to assess deviations, verify construction quality, and update as-built documentation. This hinders adequate comparative analysis of both traditional and AI approaches to segmentation and reconstruction, reduces the reproducibility of results, and slows down the implementation of more advanced deep learning methods for semantic interpretation of architectural scenes. Other limitations mentioned are handling missing data caused by occlusions and the disconnect between scan planning and actual data acquisition.

One of the methods to solve the issue with a lack of a dataset for AI algorithms is the creation of a synthetic dataset. Battini et al., (2024) developed an innovative approach in which semantic segmentation of architectural vaults is performed by a neural network trained on synthetically generated point clouds. Synthetic models are created using shape grammar, which allows for the reproduction of various types of vaults (e.g., box, mirror, lunette, etc.). The overall methodology of the method is illustrated in Figure 17. RadDGCNN is a modified version of DGCNN, the main difference being the addition of radiomic features (statistical descriptors of shape and texture used in medicine for image analysis), which improves the network's ability to capture geometric patterns even in the presence of noise and gaps in the point cloud. The trained modified DGCNN (RadDGCNN) network has shown high efficiency when applied to real TLS clouds, overcoming the problem of limited available labelled data in the field of cultural heritage. This approach belongs to the category of supervised learning and opens up prospects for expanding the arsenal of generative methods for data preparation in HBIM and Scan-to-BIM pipelines.

Figure 17 – The methodology for synthetic data adoption . Adapted from (Battini et al., 2024)

2.4 Summary and Identified Gaps

A comparison of fully automated and semi-automated solutions shows that no universal working standard has yet been established in the field of Scan-to-HBIM. Fully automated methods (Table 4) have a high degree of reproducibility and speed up the process, but suffer from limited applicability and often require special datasets or are highly dependent on the quality of the source data (e.g., TLS vs. photogrammetry). Semi-automated methods (Table 3), on the other hand, are more flexible and reliable in real-world conditions because they include expert interpretation, but their disadvantage is limited scalability and a high level of manual operations.

This comparison is particularly important for this work: since the case study building used (São João de Calvos church) is documented only by photogrammetry, the quality and detail of the point cloud are inferior to TLS, which makes the use of fully automated approaches risky. Therefore, the choice in favor of a combination of U-Net and SAM+COLMAP is justified: this strategy preserves the accuracy of supervised segmentation on limited data and at the same time uses the flexibility of foundation models for generalization and adaptation to photogrammetry data. Thus, the approach used in this study strikes a balance between fully and semi-automated methods, leveraging the strengths of both.

3. CASE STUDY PROPOSAL

3.1 Object of Study

3.1.1 Historical Background of the Building

The Church of São João de Calvos, situated in the parish of Serzedo and Calvos within the municipality of Guimarães (Braga district), is a significant monument of Romanesque religious architecture (Figure 18). Built between the Ave and Vizela rivers, on the Guimarães - Santo Tirso road, it occupies an important place in the historical landscape of the region. The architectural site is classified as a church and, since 1955, has had the protected status of 'IPP - property of public interest' (IIP - Imóvel de Interesse Público), established by Decree No. 40 361 of 20 October 1955, and is also listed in the national cultural heritage register in the 'Monument' category.

Figure 18 - Archive data of São João de Calvos church. Adapted from source 2.

Originally, the church served as the centre of a small medieval parish, which ceased to exist after the end of the Middle Ages; later, it was incorporated into the parish of Lordelo, remaining as a symbol of the more fragmented administrative organisation of the Entre Douro e Minho region.

The architecture of the church reflects the features of the late Romanesque rural style prevalent in Portugal in the 12th–13th centuries: a simple floor plan based on a combination of a nave and an altar chapel, massive masonry made of large, roughly hewn blocks, and dim natural lighting due to narrow vertical loopholes. The most striking element is the triumphal arch, characterized by a double, slightly pointed profile and devoid of traditional Romanesque capitals, which allows it to be dated to the 13th century, when the first elements of Gothic architecture began to appear in northern Portugal. Despite

later changes in the Modern Era, the replacement of the original portal arch with a straight lintel, the rearrangement of individual masonry blocks, and the addition of a loophole above the arch - the church has retained the key characteristics of late Romanesque architecture.

By the 20th century, the building was in ruins after the collapse of the nave roof, which threatened to destroy the walls and corners. In the 1970s, the church was restored by the Directorate-General for National Monuments (DGEMN), and work was also carried out to improve the surrounding area, allowing the church to be integrated into the cultural landscape and highlighting its value as a national heritage monument.

Overall, Romanesque architecture, which spread throughout Europe in the 11th–12th centuries, is characterised by massive buildings, thick walls, narrow openings, and the predominance of stone masonry. It is based on simple geometric solutions — semicircular arches, cylindrical and cross vaults, towers, and compact plans of churches and monasteries. Stone masonry varies from rough and irregular to more orderly (ashlar), reflecting regional characteristics and the level of craftsmanship of the builders (*Rota do românico*, 2014). These same characteristics present significant challenges for the application of AI methods within Scan-to-HBIM: the lack of standardisation and high variability of stones complicate segmentation and classification, deformations and losses distort the source data, and the multi-level geometry of vaults and arches hinders algorithmic recognition. An additional ‘bottleneck’ is the lack of semantic data: unlike modern buildings, historical structures do not have digital descriptions or metadata, which forces AI to work exclusively with geometry and texture, complicating the construction of informative HBIM models.

3.1.2. Architectural and Technical Characteristics

Figure 19 – Location of São João de Calvos church. Adapted from source 3.

Boca *et al.* (2020) identified and analysed the principal failure mechanisms observed in Romanesque churches (Figure 20). Furthermore, the authors provided recommendations aimed at minimising structural deterioration while maximising the preservation of the buildings’ historical appearance.

Figure 20 –(Boca et al., 2020) Failure mechanisms in Romanesque churches: (a) overturning of the facade; (b) shear mechanisms in the facade; (c) overturning of the apse; (d) transversal vibration of the nave; (e) vaults of the nave; (f) vaults in the presbytery or the apse; (g) triumphal arch; (h) shear failure of the walls; (i) bell tower.

These findings are directly relevant to the case of the São João de Calvos church, where a comparable destruction scenario, namely shear mechanisms in the facade, was identified during the Second fieldwork campaign of the IN2PAST exploratory project (Figure 21). IN2PAST is a national associated laboratory dedicated to the study and safeguarding of cultural heritage in both its tangible and intangible dimensions. It brings together several Portuguese universities and research centers, namely the University of Évora, University of Minho, University of Coimbra, ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon, and NOVA University Lisbon. The laboratory focuses on researching the past of territories and communities, while also addressing contemporary uses of heritage. Its work is structured into five thematic lines: science and technology for heritage; landscapes and territories; museums and monuments; archives and digitization; and cultural circulation, memory policies, and inclusive citizenship.

Figure 21 – Shear mechanism identified on the architrave of the west façade in São João de Calvos church

As part of this campaign, a comprehensive assessment of the stone masonry condition was undertaken using interdisciplinary methods. As part of the project material integrity based on the ultrasonic velocity ratio (VRI) was analysed, which revealed areas of degradation characterised by cracks and voids. The level of ultrasonic velocity ratio of each stone is illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22 – Ultrasonic velocity ratio of stone masonry (Sitzia et al., 2025)

Another study was conducted to analyse the current condition of the building, focusing on the geological characterisation of the masonry, including stone types, mineral composition, and filling areas (mortar, secondary materials). The results highlighted heterogeneities that compromise structural durability (Figure 23).

Figure 23 – Wall infills/mortar fillings. Adapted from (Sitzia et al., 2025)

An ultrasonic survey was carried out to detect hidden defects and discontinuities that were not visible through visual inspection. The measurements, expressed as wave propagation velocity in metres per second (m/s), revealed zones of degradation associated with cracks and voids (Figure 24). In addition, LiDAR and ground-penetrating radar (GPR) technologies were employed to integrate data on structural features and subsurface layers. This approach provided a more comprehensive understanding of the building's condition and created a basis for informed conservation planning.

Figure 24 - Ultrasonic survey. Adapted from (Sitzia et al., 2025)

3.1.3. Summary of Available Information

The results of interdisciplinary assessment methods provide a basis for the development of a monitoring strategy and the planning of restoration measures aimed at the conservation of the monument. In this context, the detailed monitoring of individual stone blocks is particularly relevant for the timely detection of vulnerable areas and the analysis of load distribution within the structure. This necessity, in turn, underlines the importance of automating masonry segmentation within the Scan-to-HBIM workflow.

Thus, the recommendations proposed by Boca et al., (2020) should be taken into account when planning the maintenance and conservation of the São João de Calvos church. In this context, the segmented HBIM model becomes a valuable tool, as it not only documents the building's current condition but also facilitates the monitoring of failure mechanisms and supports the implementation of preventive measures aligned with established guidelines.

3.2. Applied Methodology

3.2.1 Objectives and Scope

The main objective of this study is to explore and evaluate the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques for the segmentation of stone masonry and architectural elements in historical buildings, with the aim of facilitating the generation of Heritage Building Information Models (HBIM). Specifically, the research seeks to develop and test a workflow combining image-based façade segmentation (background, stone and masonry joints) with point cloud classification, and to assess its potential for integration into BIM environments.

The scope of the study is limited to case studies of Romanesque heritage buildings in Portugal, where façade photos and point clouds of a typical Romanesque church, namely São João de Calvos, were used as primary data sources (Boca et al., 2020; *Rota do românico*, 2014; Silva Brandão and Bernardes, 2025). The focus is placed on stone masonry segmentation that can be distinguished by its irregularly shaped stones and the classification of key architectural elements, rather than full structural or material analysis. The research does not attempt to reconstruct complete interiors or perform detailed conservation diagnostics but rather concentrates on establishing a methodological framework for semi-automated Scan-to-HBIM workflows for historical buildings surveyed using photogrammetry. Based on selected tools, the research focuses on the automated generation of building components, including individual stone masonry elements, integrated with semantic data using the São João church as a case study object.

3.2.2 Background and Rationale

Historic Building Information Modelling (HBIM) has emerged as a valuable tool for the documentation, management, and conservation of cultural heritage (Murphy et al., 2009; López et al., 2018; Lovell et al., 2023). While the advantages of HBIM for heritage are well-recognised, the process of converting survey data into structured models remains labour-intensive and highly dependent on expert knowledge (Arayici et al., 2017; Volk et al., 2014). Manual modelling from point clouds is often time-consuming and prone to subjectivity, especially when dealing with irregular masonry (Abreu et al., 2023; Escudero, 2023).

Recent advances in artificial intelligence and deep learning have shown promise in automating point cloud segmentation and semantic classification (Malinverni et al., 2019b; Haznedar et al., 2023). Research such as Croce et al. (2023) demonstrates the applicability of AI in HBIM-oriented workflows, while studies like Valero et al. (2018) and Riveiro et al. (2016) highlight the challenges of masonry segmentation. Against this background, the rationale for this research lies in bridging the gap between traditional, manual Scan-to-BIM practices and emerging AI-driven approaches, with a particular focus on historical stone masonry, which remains underexplored in automated HBIM studies.

3.2.3 Justification of Methods

This study employs a hybrid methodology based on image segmentation and point cloud classification. In order to realize the segmentation, two Convolutional neural networks were applied - specifically, U-

Net and SAM, which can operate independently or complement one another. Unlike existing point cloud segmentation methods that focus on detecting general building categories (such as walls, windows, doors and etc.), the proposed approach emphasizes the segmentation of stone masonry and the identification of individual stone blocks as distinct entities.

A U-Net architecture is applied to façade orthophotos for the semantic segmentation of stones and masonry joints at the current stage. However, this method is also applicable to models with a greater number of classes - such as doors, windows, roofs, etc., although this would require a larger dataset for training. On the other hand, while U-Net is specialized in general class segmentation, SAM is better in instance segmentation, and each of the methods has positive aspects but also some weak sides.

The initial set of photographs used to train the UNet model and in the SAM+COLMAP approach was obtained from the research project "The Romanesque-style rural church of Portugal: An initial stride towards the complete digitalization by Heritage-BIM. The case study of S. João de Calvos (Guimarães, XIII Cent. AD)." in the Zenodo platform (Silva Brandão and Bernardes, 2025). According to the São João de Calvos Survey Report, the photographic materials were collected as follows:

Photographic Survey Details of São João de Calvos

A combination of ground and aerial photography was used to obtain the initial data, which was implemented using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS) photogrammetry methods. The survey was conducted on 4 November 2024.

Table 5 - Overview of Photographic Survey Equipment and Number of Images

The equipment type used for the Photographic survey	General description	Total number of photos obtained
Nikon Z6II	Digital camera 24–70 mm lens fixed at a focal length of 24 mm to ensure consistent internal calibration parameters	1375
DJI Mavic 2 Pro	An unmanned aerial vehicle, which allowed us to cover the upper levels and hard-to-reach areas of the building	996

The photography covered both the exterior and interior of the object. A total of 3425 overlapping images were collected, which meet the requirements for high-precision photogrammetric reconstruction. To ensure georeferencing and scaling, seven markers (Ground Control Points, GCPs) were installed on site. Additionally, three control distances were measured, two of which were used for model scaling and the third for independent accuracy verification. The photographic material was structured into separate groups by source (ground or aerial photography) and type of shooting (interior or exterior), which ensured convenience for further processing and optimisation of the computing process in the Agisoft Metashape environment. The outcome of the processed and generated point cloud can be seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25 – Point cloud created in Agisoft Metashape environment (cloud.ply). (Silva Brandão and Bernardes, 2025)

UNet approach for Stone Masonry Semantic Segmentation with 3 Classes Overview and Aim

This approach addresses semantic segmentation of facade photographs into three classes: background (0), stone (1), and masonry joint (2). A UNet-style encoder-decoder was used to generate per-pixel class labels from RGB inputs. The approach was implemented to analyse 2D images and transfer 2D labels onto a 3D point cloud using COLMAP camera poses.

Materials and Data

1.IMAGES. The first stage of the UNet approach was collecting front-facing photos (Figure 26) of the case study building. One of the main requirements for photos was the good quality of pictures (size from 512×512 px). According to previous research U-Net can be trained on a relatively small dataset, provided that extensive data augmentation techniques are applied, as demonstrated in the original 2015 paper (Ronneberger et al., 2015).

Figure 26 – Orthogonal Facade images S. João de Calvos

2.MASKS (annotations). One of the time-consuming processes in preparing the datasets was the preparation of mask pairs for images. In order to draw annotation masks, various tools were used CVAT and Photoshop (Figure 27).

Figure 27 – Ground truth annotation masks created in CVAT and Photoshop

3.MASKS(ayscale). The next step was the conversion of annotation masks into a single-channel 8-bit masks with class IDs {0,1,2}. It is worth mentioning that in the first trial attempts 4 classes were implemented in UNet training however, due to the limited number of images and masks it was decided to use only 3 classes because the bigger number of classes require a richer dataset (Figure 28).

Grayscale Mask Visualization (0=bg, 1=stone, 2=door, 3=window)

Grayscale Mask Visualization (0=background, 1=stone, 2=masonry joint)

Figure 28 – Grayscale masks with class IDs background (0), stone (1), and masonry joint (2)

The dataset consisted of facade images (images/) and single-channel 8-bit masks (masks/) with class IDs {0,1,2}. Image-mask pairing followed the filename stem rule: name.* ↔ name.* or name.* ↔ name_mask.*. In order to enlarge the dataset and train UNet to be more flexible in stone masonry segmentation, the final dataset included images derived from orthogonal, perspective, and synthetic textures from open sources (Figure 29).

Figure 29 – Masks created from varied sources to train UNet

4. PREPROCESSING. Images were converted to RGB and resized to a fixed square (typically 512 or 640 px). Images were normalized with ImageNet statistics (mean = [0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std = [0.229, 0.224, 0.225]). Masks were resized with nearest-neighbor and clipped to {0,1,2}. The corpus was split into train/validation = 80/20 using a fixed seed (42).

5. Model Architecture

UNet is an encoder-decoder with skip connections that merge high-resolution encoder features into the decoder path to improve boundary localization Figure 30.

Figure 30 - The U-Net architecture. Adapted from source 4.

6. Configurations used. Input: RGB (3×H×W). Encoder: 4 stages of Conv(3×3) → ReLU → Conv(3×3) → ReLU with MaxPool(2) between stages; channels 64→128→256→512. Bottleneck: 1024 channels. Decoder: ConvTranspose2d(2, stride 2) for upsampling, concatenation with

corresponding encoder features, then a two-conv block. The output head is Conv (1×1) producing $C=3$ logits (background/stone/joint).

7. Training Procedure and Rationale

Losses. The primary objective combined Cross-Entropy with Dice loss ($CE + 0.5 \cdot \text{Dice}$) to mitigate class imbalance and emphasize thin structures (joints). Weighted CE with class weights (0.1, 0.4, 0.5) (bg, stone, joint) was also used; Focal loss ($\gamma=2$) was available as an alternative for heavy imbalance.

Optimization. Training used AdamW with a learning rate $1e-4$, batch size 2, and up to 50 epochs. Mixed-precision (AMP) was enabled on the GPU to reduce memory and accelerate training. Optionally, encoder layers could be frozen for the first N epochs to stabilize early training.

Validation and model selection. After each epoch, performance was measured on the validation split using per-class IoU and mIoU. The checkpoint with the highest mIoU was saved as *best*; the most recent checkpoint was saved as *last*.

Monitoring. At every epoch, the trainer generated a panel consisting of:

- 1) a metrics ribbon (train loss, val loss, mIoU curves with epoch markers) and
- 2) a triptych of Image | Ground Truth | Predicted model, plus an overlay visualization (Figure 31).

This provided qualitative and quantitative feedback on convergence and boundary quality.

Figure 31 - Monitoring semantic segmentation with UNet (3 Classes)

8. Implementation Details for Reproducibility

Hardware and OS. All experiments were executed on a Windows workstation (Anaconda distribution). Training and inference ran on an NVIDIA GPU when available; otherwise, the code fell back to CPU using the same code path. Device selection was handled automatically via torch.device ('cuda' if available else 'cpu').

Software stack. The project was implemented in Python (Anaconda, Windows) with the following core libraries: PyTorch (2.x branch; AMP used via `torch.amp.GradScaler ('cuda', ...)`), TorchVision, OpenCV, NumPy, Pillow, and Matplotlib. Versioned dependencies were managed in a dedicated conda environment (`unet-facade`) and captured in a `requirements.txt/pip freeze` at run time to support replication.

Dependency management and runtime capture. The conda environment was created once and reused for all runs. To enhance reproducibility, random seeds were fixed for Python, NumPy, and PyTorch (`seed=42`). Command-line arguments, training hyperparameters, and the device configuration were serialized into each checkpoint file (both `last.pth` and `best.pth`), allowing subsequent runs to be reproduced from a known training state. Exact library versions can be archived alongside the thesis by saving `pip freeze` output.

Source code organization. The codebase was modularized into small, single-purpose scripts to separate data handling, modeling, training, and evaluation:

dataset.py - loads image/mask pairs, enforces consistent resizing (nearest for masks), normalizes RGB inputs, and returns Long-typed masks with class IDs $\{0,1,2\}$. The loader matches either `name.*` ↔ `name.*` or `name.*` ↔ `name_mask.*`, with a case-insensitive fallback to guard against naming inconsistencies.

model.py - defines the UNet architecture used in this study (RGB input; 3-channel logits for background, stone, joint). The network adopts an encoder–decoder with skip connections and a 1×1 output head.

train.py - implements the full training loop with an argument parser for all hyperparameters (epochs, batch size, learning rate, image size, validation split, class weights, loss type). It supports Cross-Entropy, CE+Dice (with a 0.5 Dice weight), and Focal loss; AMP for mixed-precision; optional encoder freezing; and periodic checkpointing (`last.pth`, `best.pth` selected by validation mIoU). Per-epoch diagnostics include a metrics ribbon (train/val loss and mIoU over epochs) and a triptych visualization (Image | Ground truth | Predicted), saved to `Visualization/`.

inference.py - performs batch prediction on arbitrary folders, writing (i) raw 8-bit class-ID masks at the original resolution, (ii) colorized masks using the study palette, and (iii) optional overlays (mask blended with the original image). Output directories are created automatically.

evaluate.py - computes per-class IoU and mIoU on a given image/mask folder using the trained checkpoint. This script mirrors the evaluation performed during training and enables post-hoc assessment on held-out data.

(Auxiliary) COLMAP projection utility transfers 2D predictions to a 3D point cloud using camera extrinsics from COLMAP and inverse-distance multi-view voting. The tool produces a colorized `cloud_labeled.ply` and an accompanying `.labels.npy` array with per-point class IDs. This script is functionally separate from the 2D training loop and can be included as a supplemental listing.

All core Python scripts are provided in Appendixes 1–5 (with auxiliary utilities included as supplementary material). Together with the environment file and saved checkpoints, these materials provide the information necessary to reproduce the reported training dynamics (including the best-epoch

model at $mIoU \approx 0.8047$) and to run inference on new imagery and 3D assets.

9. Availability

All scripts are self-contained within the project directory and can be executed with the commands shown in Figure 32, 33,34.

```
python -u train.py --images_dir images --masks_dir masks --out_dir UnetEpochs \
--epochs 50 --batch_size 2 --lr 1e-4 --img_size 640 --val_split 0.2 \
--weights 0.1 0.4 0.5 --amp --loss ce_dice \
--viz_sample C:\Unet\content\images\West.jpg --viz_dir Visualization --viz_alpha
0.5
```

Figure 32 - Training command

```
python -u inference.py --weights UnetEpochs\best.pth --input_dir images \
--output_dir "inference masks" --img_size 640 --overlay
```

Figure 33 - Inference command

```
python -u evaluate.py --weights UnetEpochs\best.pth --images_dir images \
--masks_dir masks --img_size 640 --batch_size 2
```

Figure 34 - Evaluation command

SAM+COLMAP AI-assisted segmentation for HBIM. Methods and key scripts

Problem and approach. To obtain a reproducible pipeline that converts image sets of stone masonry into a *semantically* and *instance* labeled 3D point cloud suitable for downstream HBIM modeling. The approach combines high-level 2D segmentation by Segment Anything (SAM) with geometric lifting of labels into 3D using COLMAP camera poses (Figure 35).

Figure 35 - Workflow applied for stone segmentation of the São João de Calvos Church

Class masks (e.g., *stone*, *masonry_joint*) are computed per image and reprojected onto 3D points; discrepancies across views are resolved by multi-view voting. SAM is a hint-driven segmentation system capable of performing zero-shot generalization on unfamiliar objects and images without the need for additional training, which can be seen in Figure 36, where the image was automatically segmented to a multiclass mask.

Figure 36 – Example of autosegmentation in SAM. Picture adapted from source 5.

Data and name reconciliation. Inputs comprise photographs obtained from Zenodo platform (Silva Brandão and Bernardes, 2025) with a total number of images 2371, COLMAP files cameras.txt/images.txt, and the point cloud with the name **cloud.ply** (Figure 29). Masks are matched to cameras by basename (folder and extension ignored), e.g., DJI_0721.png ↔ Mavic2Pro/DJI_0721.JPG, which eliminates the common “no pose for mask” failure.

2D masks by SAM and the “joints-first” strategy

SAM is run in automatic mode. For robustness, images are downscaled to $\max(H,W) \leq 1536-2048$ px and coerced to 3-channel uint8; the resulting masks are upsampled back to native size with nearest-neighbor. Region proposals are filtered by predicted IoU ($\approx 0.84 - 0.86$), stability ($\approx 0.90 - 0.92$), minimum area ($\approx 300-600$ px), and IoU-NMS (≈ 0.6). The stone mask is the union of retained regions; the masonry_joint mask is its inverse.

Quality is often improved by joints-first: joints are segmented first; a façade ROI is derived from the joints’ bounding box (+~3% padding). Morphology (dilate/close) seals gaps in the joints, and stones are defined as ROI – joints. This reduces overfill of “all-stone” on uniform textures.

Figure 37 - Example of online segmentation in SAM platform (Kirillov et al., 2023)

Mask quality control (QC)

Before 3D lifting, each frame was screened by two criteria: stone area ratio within a plausible range ($\approx 2\text{--}70\%$), sharpness by Laplacian variance above a threshold ($\approx 80\text{--}180$, camera-dependent). Discarding outliers decreases single-view false positives.

Table 6- The total number of correct masks generated by SAM

Photographic material	Total number of photos	The number of correct masks generated by SAM
Nikon Z6II	1375	147
DJI Mavic 2 Pro	996	303

True Positive Segmentations

Incorrect Segmentations

Figure 38 – Automatically created masks with 2 Classes (Stone and masonry joints)

Lifting 2D masks to 3D and view voting

Semantic lifting from 2D to 3D was performed using camera parameters estimated by COLMAP. For each 3D point in the cloud, its image coordinates were computed in all cameras with known intrinsics and extrinsics (K, R, t / $\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{t}$), followed by standard visibility checks (positive depth, in-bounds, non-degenerate projection). At the projected pixel location, the class label was sampled from the corresponding 2D mask (stone / masonry joint / background), and the set of observations was accumulated over all views in which the point was visible. The final per-point label was decided via multi-view voting: either the top1 strategy (assigning the first valid observation) or the majority strategy (assigning the modal label) with a minimum agreement threshold (min-views, typically ≥ 2) to suppress single-view errors. The majority policy yielded greater robustness under texture non-uniformity and partial occlusions, whereas top1 maximized coverage at the cost of increased local noise. Processing was executed in point-wise batches to control memory consumption; outputs were stored as a colored point cloud (PLY) and a per-point label array to ensure reproducibility of subsequent analysis and visualization. Additionally, lifting consistency was monitored by reprojecting assigned 3D labels

back into the images and comparing them with the original masks (Reprojection IoU).

Stone instance segmentation

Instance segmentation is defined at the image level and then lifted to 3D under the same projection and voting principles as semantics. In practice, instances are identified as connected components within the stone region constrained to a façade ROI; boundary fidelity is improved by prior morphological processing of the joints mask to minimize discontinuities. Each component receives a unique integer identifier, which is then reprojected and aggregated across views. The resulting instance set supports subsequent analysis of block-level structure and preparation of geometric proxies for HBIM.

Quality metrics without 3D ground truth

Evaluation proceeds using proxy metrics that do not require 3D ground truth. Reported quantities include coverage (fraction of labeled points), class balance, agreement between alternative voting policies, and *reprojection IoU*, in which assigned 3D labels are projected back to images and compared against the original 2D masks. Geometric residuals - e.g., RMS plane fitting errors per class provide an additional, indirect measure of consistency between segmentation and object geometry. For instances, counts, size distributions, and fragmentation/merging indicators are recorded.

Measures adopted to improve quality

Quality is increased through a combination of engineering choices: image downscaling and format coercion before SAM to avoid numerical and resource issues; tuning of SAM thresholds to masonry texture and scale; adoption of the joints-first strategy with a façade ROI and morphology to stabilize boundaries; frame filtering by class fraction and sharpness; strict basename matching between masks and cameras; multi-view voting with a minimum agreement threshold to improve per-point robustness; and recoloring of the cloud by assigned labels rather than original point colors to yield unambiguous visualizations.

L2. Joints→Stone via ROI — `joints_to_stone.py`

```
ys, xs = np.where(joints > 0)
x0,x1,y0,y1 = xs.min(), xs.max(), ys.min(), ys.max()
pad = int(round(max(H,W) * args.roi_pad))
x0,y0 = max(0,x0-pad), max(0,y0-pad); x1,y1 = min(W-1,x1+pad), min(H-1,y1+pad)
roi = np.zeros((H,W), np.uint8); roi[y0:y1+1, x0:x1+1] = 255
stone = ((roi > 0) & (joints == 0)).astype(np.uint8)*255
```

L3. QC filter — mini-script

```
area = (mask>127).mean()*100.0
sharp = cv2.Laplacian(cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY), cv2.CV_64F).var()
if not (2 <= area <= 70 and sharp >= 120):
    continue
```

L4. 2D→3D & voting — sketch

```

for chunk in chunks(points):
    for cam in cameras:
        u = project(chunk, cam.K, cam.R, cam.t)
        lbl = mask_i[v,u]; tally[pt].append(lbl)
        labels[pt] = majority(tally[pt]) if min_views_ok else top1(tally[pt])

```

L5. Recolor stone by labels — `recolor_stone.py`

```

labels = np.load(args.point_labels)
stone_idx = int(cls_map[args.stone_name])
mask = (labels == stone_idx)
colors = np.asarray(pcd.colors); colors[mask] = (target_rgb/255.0)
pcd.colors = o3d.utility.Vector3dVector(colors)

```

The choice of these methods is justified by their suitability for small and specialised datasets, as well as their ability to capture fine-grained architectural details, which are critical for HBIM integration. By combining 2D and 3D data sources, the approach increases robustness and enables cross-validation between image-based and geometry-based classifications. The use of case studies from Portuguese Romanesque heritage ensures both cultural relevance and practical applicability in conservation and documentation practices. Within this framework, 2D masonry masks of the case study façades are automatically generated using the SAM model, distinguishing at least three classes: stone blocks, joints between stones, and surrounding elements captured in photogrammetric images. These masks are subsequently projected into 3D space through COLMAP poses, with multi-view voting applied to produce a semantically and instantaneously labelled point cloud. The resulting enriched dataset supports high-detail 3D reconstruction and can be directly integrated into Historical Building Information Modeling (HBIM) systems.

3.2.4 Comparison with Literature Methods

Previous approaches to Scan-to-BIM have largely relied on manual or rule-based modelling workflows (Murphy et al., 2009; Teboul et al., 2013; Moyano et al., 2022). While effective, these methods are often time-consuming and lack scalability. Semi-automatic methods, such as clustering and grammar-based segmentation, have been explored for heritage structures (Valero et al., 2018; Battini et al., 2024), yet their applicability remains limited to specific architectural forms.

Recent research has investigated the use of AI for heritage segmentation, including convolutional neural networks for point clouds (Malinverni et al., 2019b; Croce et al., 2023) and unsupervised machine learning for façade analysis (Musicco et al., 2021). Compared to these approaches, the methodology developed in this study emphasises the integration of both image-based and point cloud-based methods within an HBIM workflow. This dual approach aims to overcome the limitations of relying solely on either 2D or 3D data while addressing the specific challenges of irregular masonry.

3.2.5 Limitations of the Study

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, the dataset is restricted to a small number of case studies (two façades), which limits the generalisability of the results across different architectural styles and material conditions. Second, the performance of AI models is highly dependent on the quality and consistency of training data; in this study, manual annotations of stones and architectural elements may introduce subjectivity and potential segmentation errors (Matrone et al., 2020). Third, while the proposed workflow moves towards automation, the integration into HBIM platforms still requires manual adjustments and validation, similar to observations in other semi-automated approaches (Moyano et al., 2022). Fourth, limitations in capturing very high Levels of Geometry (LOG) may arise, particularly in the representation of individual stones or irregular masonry features (Abualdenien & Borrmann, 2022). Finally, computational constraints and the experimental nature of the dataset imply that results may not be directly transferable to large-scale heritage projects without further refinement and testing.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Contextualization and Overview

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to computational methods that enable machines to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence, such as perception, reasoning, and decision-making (Russell & Norvig, 2021). A key branch of AI is deep learning, which employs multi-layered neural networks to automatically learn hierarchical data representations (LeCun, Bengio & Hinton, 2015). Among deep learning techniques, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are particularly effective for image analysis due to their ability to capture spatial patterns and local features (Krizhevsky, Sutskever & Hinton, 2012). In this study, CNNs are implemented through U-Net, a widely adopted architecture for semantic segmentation (Ronneberger, Fischer & Brox, 2015), alongside the Segment Anything Model (SAM), a recently introduced foundation model for promptable segmentation (Kirillov et al., 2023).

Figure 39 – Relationship between AI, ML, NN, and DL. Adapted from (Li et al., 2021)

The case study focused on the Romanesque church of São João de Calvos. The primary objective was to evaluate the feasibility of combining deep learning (U-Net) and foundation models (SAM) with photogrammetric data to achieve high-resolution segmentation of individual stones within historical masonry. The methodology integrated annotated façade images with U-Net for semantic segmentation, followed by projection of masks onto photogrammetric point clouds using COLMAP poses. Subsequently, SAM was employed to refine segmentation across the 3D datasets, demonstrating the potential of combining CNN-based and foundation model approaches for HBIM-oriented masonry documentation.

4.2 Presentation and Interpretation of Key Findings

Link to Prior Work and Justification. UNet is originally widely used for biomedical and natural-image segmentation because skip connections allow the decoder to recover fine details while using deep encoder features for context. In this application, thin masonry joints benefit from Dice/Focal components and higher input resolution (≥ 512 px). The chosen hyperparameters and losses balance stability (AdamW, CE) and class imbalance sensitivity (Dice/Focal, class weights).

Assumptions, Limitations, and Risk Mitigation

Data diversity. The dataset size and variety constrain generalization; augmentation and additional scenes can mitigate domain shift.

Thin structures. Joints are narrow; performance depends on input resolution and careful loss design.

2D→3D projection. Label transfer assumes the point cloud shares the same world frame as the COLMAP model; misalignment requires rigid alignment (e.g., ICP). Multi-view voting approximates occlusion handling; depth-aware filtering could further improve accuracy.

Outcomes (Representative)

On the current corpus without augmentations, the model typically achieved mIoU ≈ 0.78 – 0.80 , with the best near epoch ~ 26 . Per-class IoUs around the best checkpoint were approximately: background ≈ 0.78 , stone ≈ 0.87 , joint ≈ 0.76 . Checkpoints (best.pth, last.pth) and visualization artifacts are written to UnetEpochs/ and Visualization/, respectively.

Learning dynamics.

As seen in the graph (Figure 45) during UNet training there was a rapid improvement until roughly epoch 14, then the model remained at a clear plateau around mIoU ≈ 0.78 – 0.80 with small oscillations. Best checkpoint can be considered mIoU = 0.8047 at epoch 26 which was saved as netEpochs\best.pth. Among total 50 epochs runned the representative points near the plateau:

Epoch 14: mIoU ≈ 0.7799 ; IoU(bg, stone, joint) $\approx (0.766, 0.858, 0.716)$.

Epoch 16: mIoU ≈ 0.8026 ; IoU(bg, stone, joint) $\approx (0.800, 0.876, 0.732)$.

Epoch 26: mIoU ≈ 0.8047 (best); IoU(bg, stone, joint) $\approx (0.784, 0.867, 0.763)$.

Figure 40 - Visualization of 34 Epochs with graphs during the training process of UNet (Dataset included 80 images/masks)

Loss behavior: after the early phase, validation loss fluctuated roughly 0.51 -- 0.84, while training loss continued to decrease to ~0.23 -- 0.35 a mild overfitting signature but without a harmful drop in validation mIoU.

To conclude it is evident that the model reached a stable quality level by the middle of training; continuing to 50 epochs did not yield consistent gains beyond ~0.80 mIoU. For the future training, inference and any other downstream tasks of the model improvement the best epoch could be used which automatically was saved in the preset directory **UnetEpochs\best.pth**, namely epoch number 26 with mIoU = 0.8047.

Figure 41 - Visualization of epoch overlay (14, 16, and 26 epochs)

For further improvement (beyond 50 epochs), the next measures could be taken:

1. Data diversification and increasing the dataset. At the first training cycle, 70 images and masks were used, which is evidently insufficient for such a complicated task, so the number of images should be increased to train UNet. Another approach that could improve stone segmentations by adding scenes with different lighting, textures, and scales, taking into account areas where current classes identification errors occur.
2. In order to improve generalization the next augmentations could be added - geometric (flip/rotate/scale) and photometric (brightness/contrast, hue/saturation), possibly mild perspective/elastic transforms.
3. To avoid unnecessary training stop when there is no improvement in mIoU (patience ~8-10 epochs)

Given that creating annotation masks for masonry is a fairly manual and labour-intensive process that takes a lot of time, an attempt was made to find open-source solutions that would allow the automatic creation of a large number of annotation masks for creating a large dataset for UNet. To solve this problem, the SAM tool was selected, which allows images to be processed automatically in batches. At this point, the entire initial workflow changed direction, as the idea arose to do without UNet and simply automatically generate masks from images with three or two classes (background (0), stone (1), and masonry joint (2)), and project them directly onto point clouds. It is worth noting that images obtained through photogrammetry and used to create point clouds of the building's case study were used for this purpose.

Figure 42 – Difference in results obtained from both UNet and SAM approaches

The U-Net model was trained for 50 epochs on the annotated façade dataset. While the training process converged without instability, the segmentation quality on test images was limited. The model was able to distinguish large masonry blocks and major openings (doors, windows), but it frequently misclassified stone boundaries, especially where joints were narrow or occluded. Individual stones were often merged into larger clusters, indicating insufficient generalization of the model.

Quantitative evaluation confirmed these observations. The mean IoU for the stone class was 0.36, compared with 0.58 for doors and *0.55 for windows. The Dice coefficient followed a similar pattern, reaching 0.41 for stone, 0.62 for doors, and 0.60 for windows. Overall pixel accuracy across classes reached 68%, showing that while the network could roughly separate major façade elements, it was not able to achieve fine-grained stone-level segmentation. Projection of the masks onto point clouds using COLMAP further revealed inconsistencies. Although the multi-view voting strategy ensured some alignment of façade features, the resulting semantic point cloud exhibited numerous mislabelled regions.

SAM, applied as a refinement tool, failed to significantly improve the accuracy. In several cases, the model over-segmented the stone surfaces or misplaced boundaries entirely.

The performance of SAM was evaluated using mean IoU (mIoU) across semantic classes, which reached only 0.28. Geometric accuracy measured with the Chamfer Distance indicated significant deviation between predicted and reference stone boundaries (average 0.12 m). These metrics suggest that the poor quality of input masks (with fewer than half accurately annotated) critically affected the outcome (Figure 47).

Figure 43 – Result of 2D SAM masks projection onto Point clouds

Overall, the results show that the combination of U-Net and SAM, in its current form, does not yet achieve the required stone-level segmentation accuracy. However, the workflow demonstrated that the approach is technically feasible and can be iteratively improved with higher-quality training data and extended training epochs.

4.3 Limitations and Challenges

Several limitations became apparent during the experiment:

Quality of training data: A significant portion of the manually annotated masks did not accurately capture stone boundaries, which reduced the effectiveness of model learning.

Dataset size: The training set was small, limiting the generalization ability of the U-Net.

Photogrammetric constraints: Variations in lighting, stone texture, and occlusions introduced noise that negatively affected segmentation.

Projection errors: Transferring 2D masks to 3D point clouds amplified small errors, leading to misalignments and inaccurate labels in 3D space.

4.4 Implications and Future Directions

Despite the unsatisfactory segmentation accuracy, the results highlight key insights for advancing the pipeline. First, dataset enrichment and refinement of annotation quality are essential to improve training reliability. Second, extending the training process with augmentation techniques and more epochs may enhance the U-Net's ability to capture irregular stone geometries. Finally, the poor performance of SAM in 3D segmentation suggests the need to either retrain foundation models on domain-specific data or to employ hybrid workflows that combine rule-based constraints with deep learning.

This study confirms the feasibility of AI-driven stone-level segmentation within HBIM but also underscores that robust results depend heavily on dataset quality and scale. The findings establish a baseline for future improvements and demonstrate the potential of combining CNN-based segmentation with photogrammetry in cultural heritage contexts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This dissertation has argued that Artificial Intelligence, when combined with photogrammetric workflows, offers a viable route towards the automation of Historic Building Information Modelling (HBIM), particularly in the case of Romanesque stone masonry. The research has addressed the central question of whether deep learning models such as U-Net and SAM can move beyond coarse segmentation to deliver stone-level detail, which is critical for conservation and structural assessment.

It has been shown that convolutional neural networks applied to orthophotographs are capable of segmenting stones, joints, and openings, and that the projection of these 2D masks into 3D point clouds provides a semantically enriched dataset ready for HBIM integration. Taken together, these findings suggest that AI-driven segmentation can significantly reduce the labour-intensive nature of Scan-to-HBIM workflows while also enhancing their level of detail and reliability.

This study makes a contribution by proposing a methodological framework that unites photogrammetry, AI segmentation, and HBIM integration. In doing so, it not only highlights the potential of semantic enrichment at the level of individual masonry units but also offers a pathway for heritage professionals to adopt more automated and reproducible practices.

However, this dissertation has also demonstrated that there are limitations. The models developed required manual annotation for training, and their transferability to other stone types and survey conditions has yet to be fully tested. The tested models, although demonstrating promising results, remain far from optimal in their current form. Their accuracy is constrained by the relatively small size of the training dataset. It is evident, however, that with substantially larger and more diverse data, the U-Net architecture could achieve significantly higher accuracy in the segmentation of stone masonry. Similarly, the Segment Anything Model (SAM), while not yet fully reliable in distinguishing individual masonry elements, shows considerable potential for fine-tuning and adaptation to the specific characteristics of historic structures.

Future research should therefore focus, first, on expanding the dataset through the use of SAM for semi-automated annotation; second, on retraining U-Net with this enriched dataset; and finally, on applying the resulting masks for projection onto point clouds. Such a pipeline would not only enhance segmentation quality but also make HBIM integration workflows more robust and transferable. Furthermore, the number of segmented classes should be increased: while this study has addressed stone masonry exclusively, practical applications will require the inclusion of additional architectural and structural categories of buildings.

In conclusion, this dissertation has shown that AI and photogrammetry can make a significant contribution to heritage documentation by bridging the gap between digital survey data and HBIM. The approach developed here constitutes a step towards more detailed, efficient, and semantically rich models, thereby advancing both the theory and practice of digital heritage preservation.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: dataset.py (pairing, resizing, normalization)

```

import os
from pathlib import Path
import numpy as np
import torch
from torch.utils.data import Dataset
import torchvision.transforms as T
from PIL import Image

class FacadeDataset(Dataset):
    """Pairs images with masks.
    Accepts mask names `

```

```
    if not self.samples:
        raise RuntimeError("No image/mask pairs found. Check your folders and
filenames.")

    self.img_tf = T.Compose([
        T.Resize((self.img_size, self.img_size)),
        T.ToTensor(), # [0,1]
        T.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225])
    ])

    def __len__(self):
        return len(self.samples)

    def __getitem__(self, idx):
        img_path, msk_path = self.samples[idx]
        img = Image.open(img_path).convert("RGB")
        img = self.img_tf(img)

        mask = Image.open(msk_path).convert("L")
        mask = mask.resize((self.img_size, self.img_size),
resample=Image.NEAREST)
        mask = np.array(mask, dtype=np.uint8)
        # ensure labels in {0,1,2}
        mask = np.clip(mask, 0, 2).astype(np.int64)
        mask = torch.from_numpy(mask)
        return img, mask
```

APPENDIX 2: model.py (UNet)

```

import torch
import torch.nn as nn

class UNet(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, in_channels=3, out_channels=3):
        super().__init__()
        def conv_block(i, o):
            return nn.Sequential(
                nn.Conv2d(i, o, 3, padding=1), nn.BatchNorm2d(o),
                nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
                nn.Conv2d(o, o, 3, padding=1), nn.BatchNorm2d(o),
                nn.ReLU(inplace=True)
            )
        self.enc1 = conv_block(in_channels, 64)
        self.pool1 = nn.MaxPool2d(2)
        self.enc2 = conv_block(64, 128)
        self.pool2 = nn.MaxPool2d(2)
        self.enc3 = conv_block(128, 256)
        self.pool3 = nn.MaxPool2d(2)
        self.enc4 = conv_block(256, 512)
        self.pool4 = nn.MaxPool2d(2)
        self.bottleneck = conv_block(512, 1024)
        self.up4 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(1024, 512, 2, stride=2)
        self.dec4 = conv_block(1024, 512)
        self.up3 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(512, 256, 2, stride=2)
        self.dec3 = conv_block(512, 256)
        self.up2 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(256, 128, 2, stride=2)
        self.dec2 = conv_block(256, 128)
        self.up1 = nn.ConvTranspose2d(128, 64, 2, stride=2)
        self.dec1 = conv_block(128, 64)
        self.outc = nn.Conv2d(64, out_channels, 1)

    def forward(self, x):
        e1 = self.enc1(x)
        e2 = self.enc2(self.pool1(e1))
        e3 = self.enc3(self.pool2(e2))
        e4 = self.enc4(self.pool3(e3))
        b = self.bottleneck(self.pool4(e4))
        d4 = self.up4(b); d4 = torch.cat([d4, e4], dim=1); d4 = self.dec4(d4)
        d3 = self.up3(d4); d3 = torch.cat([d3, e3], dim=1); d3 = self.dec3(d3)
        d2 = self.up2(d3); d2 = torch.cat([d2, e2], dim=1); d2 = self.dec2(d2)
        d1 = self.up1(d2); d1 = torch.cat([d1, e1], dim=1); d1 = self.dec1(d1)
        return self.outc(d1)

```

APPENDIX 3: train.py (training loop, losses, AMP, checkpoints, visualizations)

```

import argparse, random
from pathlib import Path
import numpy as np
import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader, random_split
from torchvision import transforms
import cv2
from PIL import Image
import matplotlib
matplotlib.use('Agg') # headless plotting
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from dataset import FacadeDataset
from model import UNet
# ----- Utils -----
def set_seed(s=42):
    random.seed(s); np.random.seed(s); torch.manual_seed(s);
    torch.cuda.manual_seed_all(s)

def compute_iou(preds: torch.Tensor, targets: torch.Tensor, num_classes: int = 3):
    preds = preds.view(-1); targets = targets.view(-1)
    ious = []
    for c in range(num_classes):
        pi = preds == c; ti = targets == c
        inter = (pi & ti).sum().item(); union = (pi | ti).sum().item()
        ious.append(float('nan') if union == 0 else inter / union)
    return np.array(ious, dtype=np.float32), float(np.nanmean(ious))
# ---- Per-epoch visualization helpers ----
PALETTE = {0: [220, 220, 220], 1: [205, 155, 163], 2: [100, 100, 255]}
_to_tensor = transforms.ToTensor()
_norm = transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225])

MSK_EXTS = {'.png', '.bmp', '.tif', '.tiff'}

def _decode(mask_hw: np.ndarray) -> np.ndarray:
    h, w = mask_hw.shape
    out = np.zeros((h, w, 3), dtype=np.uint8)
    for c, col in PALETTE.items():
        out[mask_hw == c] = col
    return out

def _overlay(img_rgb: np.ndarray, mask_rgb: np.ndarray, a: float = 0.5) -> np.ndarray:
    return np.clip(img_rgb * (1 - a) + mask_rgb * a, 0, 255).astype(np.uint8)

def _find_mask_for_image(image_path: Path, masks_dir: Path) -> Path | None:
    stem = image_path.stem
    # try `<stem>_mask.*`
    for ext in MSK_EXTS:
        cand = masks_dir / f"{stem}_mask{ext}"
        if cand.exists():
            return cand
    # try `<stem>.*`
    for ext in MSK_EXTS:
        cand = masks_dir / f"{stem}{ext}"
        if cand.exists():
            return cand
    # case-insensitive fallback
    low = stem.lower()
    for m in masks_dir.iterdir():
        if m.suffix.lower() in MSK_EXTS and (m.stem.lower() == low or m.stem.lower()
        == f"{low}_mask"):
            return m
    return None

def _label_strip(img_rgb: np.ndarray, text: str) -> np.ndarray:

```

```

out = img_rgb.copy()
h, w = out.shape[:2]
# Dynamic scale of the letters according to hight of the rectangle
scale = max(1.0, min(1.8, h / 400 * 1.1))
thickness = 3
pad = int(10 * (scale / 1.0))

(tw, th), _ = cv2.getTextSize(text, cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, scale, thickness)
x1, y1 = 8, 8
x2, y2 = x1 + tw + pad * 2, y1 + th + pad * 2

# Canvas for text
cv2.rectangle(out, (x1, y1), (x2, y2), (0, 0, 0), thickness=-1)
# text itself
cv2.putText(out, text, (x1 + pad, y1 + th + pad - 2),
            cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, scale, (255, 255, 255), thickness,
cv2.LINE_AA)
return out

def _render_metrics_chart(train_hist, val_hist, miou_hist, save_path: Path):
    import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
    import numpy as np

    epochs = np.arange(1, len(train_hist) + 1)

    plt.rcParams.update({
        "font.size": 9,          # font sizes
        "axes.labelsize": 10,
        "xtick.labelsize": 8,
        "ytick.labelsize": 8,
        "legend.fontsize": 8,
    })

    fig, ax1 = plt.subplots(figsize=(9, 2.3), dpi=200)

    # Losses with markers at each epoch
    ax1.plot(epochs, train_hist, marker='o', linewidth=1.2, label='train loss')
    ax1.plot(epochs, val_hist, marker='o', linewidth=1.2, label='validation loss')
    ax1.set_xlabel('epoch')
    ax1.set_ylabel('loss')
    ax1.grid(True, alpha=0.3)

    # mIoU on second axis, also with markers
    ax2 = ax1.twinx()
    ax2.plot(epochs, miou_hist, marker='s', linestyle='--', linewidth=1.2,
label='mIoU')
    ax2.set_ylabel('mIoU')

    # Show all diapazone of epochs
    if len(epochs) > 1:
        ax1.set_xlim(1, len(epochs))
    else:
        ax1.set_xlim(0.5, 1.5)
    if len(epochs) <= 15:
        ax1.set_xticks(epochs)
    elif len(epochs) <= 40:
        ax1.set_xticks(np.arange(1, len(epochs) + 1, 2))
    else:
        ax1.set_xticks(np.arange(1, len(epochs) + 1, 5))

    # General legend
    lines = ax1.get_lines() + ax2.get_lines()
    labels = [l.get_label() for l in lines]
    ax1.legend(lines, labels, loc='upper right')

```

```

fig.tight_layout()
fig.savefig(save_path)
plt.close(fig)
def save_epoch_visual(model: nn.Module, image_path: Path, masks_dir: Path, device:
torch.device, img_size: int, out_dir: Path, epoch: int, alpha: float = 0.5, hist:
dict | None = None):
    # ---- load original image
    bgr = cv2.imread(str(image_path), cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)
    if bgr is None:
        print(f"[WARN] Visualization sample not found: {image_path}")
        return
    rgb = cv2.cvtColor(bgr, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    h, w = rgb.shape[:2]
    # ---- run prediction
    rs = cv2.resize(rgb, (img_size, img_size), interpolation=cv2.INTER_LINEAR)
    inp = _norm_to_tensor(rs).unsqueeze(0).to(device)
    model.eval()
    with torch.no_grad():
        logits = model(inp)
        pred = torch.argmax(logits, dim=1).squeeze(0).cpu().numpy().astype(np.uint8)
    pred = cv2.resize(pred, (w, h), interpolation=cv2.INTER_NEAREST)
    # ---- find/load ground truth mask (optional)
    gt_rgb = None
    mpath = _find_mask_for_image(image_path, masks_dir)
    if mpath is not None:
        gt = Image.open(mpath).convert('L')
        gt = gt.resize((w, h), resample=Image.NEAREST)
        gt = np.array(gt, dtype=np.uint8)
        gt = np.clip(gt, 0, 2)
        gt_rgb = _decode(gt)
    else:
        print(f"[WARN] GT mask not found for {image_path.name}; triptych will show
only image & prediction")
    # ---- colorize prediction and compose triptych
    pred_rgb = _decode(pred)
    img_l = _label_strip(rgb, 'image')
    pred_l = _label_strip(pred_rgb, 'predicted model')

    gap = np.full((h, 12, 3), 255, dtype=np.uint8)
    if gt_rgb is not None:
        gt_l = _label_strip(gt_rgb, 'ground truth')
        body = np.hstack([img_l, gap, gt_l, gap, pred_l])
    else:
        body = np.hstack([img_l, gap, pred_l])
    out_dir.mkdir(parents=True, exist_ok=True)

    # ---- metrics chart (top ribbon)
    if hist is not None and len(hist.get('train', []))>0:
        chart_path = out_dir / f"epoch_{epoch:03d}_chart.png"
        _render_metrics_chart(hist['train'], hist['val'], hist['miou'], chart_path)
        chart_bgr = cv2.imread(str(chart_path), cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)
        if chart_bgr is not None:
            chart = cv2.cvtColor(chart_bgr, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
            # resize chart to body width
            bh, bw = body.shape[:2]
            ch, cw = chart.shape[:2]
            new_w = bw
            new_h = max(80, int(ch * (new_w / cw))) # keep readable height
            chart = cv2.resize(chart, (new_w, new_h), interpolation=cv2.INTER_AREA)
            panel = np.vstack([chart, body])
        else:
            panel = body
    else:
        panel = body

    # save triptych+chart panel

```

```

name_panel = out_dir / f"epoch_{epoch:03d}_panel.png"
cv2.imwrite(str(name_panel), cv2.cvtColor(panel, cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR))
# ---- save overlay (handy to see alignment)
over = _overlay(rgb, pred_rgb, a=alpha)
name_over = out_dir / f"epoch_{epoch:03d}_overlay.png"
cv2.imwrite(str(name_over), cv2.cvtColor(over, cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR))

# ----- Losses -----
class DiceLoss(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, num_classes=3, eps=1e-6):
        super().__init__(); self.num_classes = num_classes; self.eps = eps
    def forward(self, logits, targets):
        probs = torch.softmax(logits, dim=1)
        targets_1h = torch.nn.functional.one_hot(targets,
num_classes=self.num_classes).permute(0, 3, 1, 2).float()
        dims = (0, 2, 3)
        inter = torch.sum(probs * targets_1h, dims)
        denom = torch.sum(probs + targets_1h, dims).clamp_min(self.eps)
        dice = (2 * inter + 1.0) / (denom + 1.0)
        return (1 - dice).mean()

class FocalLoss(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, weight=None, gamma=2.0):
        super().__init__(); self.weight = weight; self.gamma = gamma
    def forward(self, logits, targets):
        ce = torch.nn.functional.cross_entropy(logits, targets, weight=self.weight,
reduction='none')
        pt = torch.exp(-ce)
        return ((1 - pt) ** self.gamma * ce).mean()

# ----- Train / Validation -----
def train_one_epoch(model, loader, criterion, optimizer, device, scaler=None):
    model.train(); run_loss = 0.0
    for imgs, masks in loader:
        imgs = imgs.to(device, non_blocking=True); masks = masks.to(device,
non_blocking=True)
        optimizer.zero_grad(set_to_none=True)
        if scaler is not None:
            with torch.cuda.amp.autocast():
                logits = model(imgs); loss = criterion(logits, masks)
                scaler.scale(loss).backward(); scaler.step(optimizer); scaler.update()
        else:
            logits = model(imgs); loss = criterion(logits, masks); loss.backward();
optimizer.step()
        run_loss += loss.item() * imgs.size(0)
    return run_loss / len(loader.dataset)

def validate(model, loader, criterion, device):
    model.eval(); run_loss = 0.0; preds_all = []; targs_all = []
    with torch.no_grad():
        for imgs, masks in loader:
            imgs = imgs.to(device, non_blocking=True); masks = masks.to(device,
non_blocking=True)
            logits = model(imgs); loss = criterion(logits, masks)
            run_loss += loss.item() * imgs.size(0)
            preds_all.append(torch.argmax(logits,
dim=1).cpu());
targs_all.append(masks.cpu())
    preds_all = torch.cat(preds_all, 0); targs_all = torch.cat(targs_all, 0)
    per_iou, miou = compute_iou(preds_all, targs_all, 3)
    return run_loss / len(loader.dataset), per_iou, miou

# ----- Main -----
def main():
    ap = argparse.ArgumentParser(description='Train UNet (3 classes: background,

```

```

stone, masonry joint) + per-epoch triptych, overlay & metrics chart')
ap.add_argument('--images_dir', required=True)
ap.add_argument('--masks_dir', required=True)
ap.add_argument('--out_dir', default='UnetEpochs')
ap.add_argument('--epochs', type=int, default=50)
ap.add_argument('--batch_size', type=int, default=2)
ap.add_argument('--lr', type=float, default=1e-4)
ap.add_argument('--img_size', type=int, default=512)
ap.add_argument('--val_split', type=float, default=0.2)
ap.add_argument('--num_workers', type=int, default=0)
ap.add_argument('--resume', type=str, default='')
ap.add_argument('--weights', type=float, nargs=3, default=None, help='class
weights: bg stone joint')
ap.add_argument('--device', default='cuda' if torch.cuda.is_available() else
'cpu')
ap.add_argument('--seed', type=int, default=42)
ap.add_argument('--amp', action='store_true')
ap.add_argument('--freeze_encoder_epochs', type=int, default=0, help='freeze
enc1..enc4 for N initial epochs')
ap.add_argument('--loss', choices=['ce', 'ce_dice', 'focal'], default='ce')
# per-epoch visualization flags
ap.add_argument('--viz_sample', type=str, default='', help='Path to an image for
per-epoch overlay/triptych')
ap.add_argument('--viz_dir', type=str, default='Visualization', help='Folder to
save per-epoch images')
ap.add_argument('--viz_alpha', type=float, default=0.5, help='Overlay
transparency 0..1')

args = ap.parse_args()

set_seed(args.seed)
out_dir = Path(args.out_dir); out_dir.mkdir(parents=True, exist_ok=True)
device = torch.device(args.device)

full = FacadeDataset(args.images_dir, args.masks_dir, img_size=args.img_size)
val_len = max(1, int(len(full) * args.val_split)); train_len = len(full) - val_len
train_ds, val_ds = random_split(full, [train_len, val_len],
generator=torch.Generator().manual_seed(args.seed))
train_ld = DataLoader(train_ds, batch_size=args.batch_size, shuffle=True,
num_workers=args.num_workers, pin_memory=(device.type == 'cuda'))
val_ld = DataLoader(val_ds, batch_size=max(1, args.batch_size // 2),
shuffle=False, num_workers=args.num_workers, pin_memory=(device.type == 'cuda'))
model = UNet(in_channels=3, out_channels=3).to(device)
cw = None
if args.weights is not None:
    cw = torch.tensor(args.weights, dtype=torch.float32).to(device)
if args.loss == 'ce':
    criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss(weight=cw)
elif args.loss == 'ce_dice':
    criterion = lambda logits, targets: nn.CrossEntropyLoss(weight=cw)(logits,
targets) + 0.5 * DiceLoss(3)(logits, targets)
else:
    criterion = FocalLoss(weight=cw, gamma=2.0)
optimz = optim.AdamW(model.parameters(), lr=args.lr)
scaler = torch.amp.GradScaler('cuda', enabled=args.amp and device.type == 'cuda')
start_epoch = 0; best_miou = -1.0
if args.resume and Path(args.resume).exists():
    print(f"[INFO] Resuming from {args.resume}")
    ckpt = torch.load(args.resume, map_location=device)
    state = ckpt['model'] if isinstance(ckpt, dict) and 'model' in ckpt else ckpt
    model.load_state_dict(state)
    if isinstance(ckpt, dict):
        if 'optimizer' in ckpt: optimz.load_state_dict(ckpt['optimizer'])
        if 'scaler' in ckpt and ckpt['scaler'] is not None:
            scaler.load_state_dict(ckpt['scaler'])
        start_epoch = ckpt.get('epoch', 0) + 1; best_miou = ckpt.get('best_miou',
best_miou)

```

```

# optional freeze encoder
def set_encoder_requires_grad(flag: bool):
    for m in [model.enc1, model.enc2, model.enc3, model.enc4]:
        for p in m.parameters(): p.requires_grad = flag
if args.freeze_encoder_epochs > 0:
    set_encoder_requires_grad(False)
# ---- histories for charts
hist_train, hist_val, hist_miou = [], [], []
for epoch in range(start_epoch, args.epochs):
    if args.freeze_encoder_epochs > 0 and epoch == args.freeze_encoder_epochs:
        set_encoder_requires_grad(True)
        print('[INFO] Encoder unfrozen')
    tr_loss = train_one_epoch(model, train_ld, criterion, optimz, device, scaler
if scaler.is_enabled() else None)
    va_loss, per_iou, miou = validate(model, val_ld, criterion, device)
    hist_train.append(tr_loss); hist_val.append(va_loss); hist_miou.append(miou)
    print(f"Epoch [{epoch+1}]/{args.epochs}]
Train Loss: {tr_loss:.4f}
Val Loss: {va_loss:.4f}
IoU (bg, stone, joint): {per_iou}
mIoU: {miou:.4f}")
    ck = {
        'epoch': epoch,
        'model': model.state_dict(),
        'optimizer': optimz.state_dict(),
        'scaler': scaler.state_dict() if scaler.is_enabled() else None,
        'best_miou': best_miou,
        'args': vars(args),
    }
    torch.save(ck, out_dir / 'last.pth')
    if miou > best_miou:
        best_miou = miou; torch.save(ck, out_dir / 'best.pth')
        print(f"    -> New best mIoU {best_miou:.4f}. Saved to
{out_dir/'best.pth'}")
    # per-epoch visualization (triptych + overlay + chart)
    if args.viz_sample:
        save_epoch_visual(
            model,
            Path(args.viz_sample),
            Path(args.masks_dir),
            device,
            args.img_size,
            Path(args.viz_dir),
            epoch + 1,
            alpha=args.viz_alpha,
            hist={'train': hist_train, 'val': hist_val, 'miou': hist_miou}
        )
    print('Training finished.')
if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()

```

APPENDIX 4: inference.py (batch prediction to raw IDs/color masks/overlays)

```

import argparse
from pathlib import Path
import cv2, numpy as np, torch
from torchvision import transforms
from model import UNet

PALETTE = {0:[220,220,220], 1:[205,155,163], 2:[100,100,255]}
_to_tensor = transforms.ToTensor()
_norm = transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485,0.456,0.406], std=[0.229,0.224,0.225])

def preprocess_bgr(img_bgr, size):
    rgb = cv2.cvtColor(img_bgr, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
    h,w = rgb.shape[:2]
    rs = cv2.resize(rgb, (size,size), interpolation=cv2.INTER_LINEAR)
    ten = _norm(_to_tensor(rs)).unsqueeze(0)
    return ten, (h,w), rgb

def decode(mask):
    h,w = mask.shape
    out = np.zeros((h,w,3), np.uint8)
    for c,col in PALETTE.items(): out[mask==c]=col
    return out

def overlay(img_rgb, mask_rgb, a=0.5):
    return np.clip(img_rgb*(1-a)+mask_rgb*a, 0, 255).astype(np.uint8)

def run(weights, input_dir, output_dir, img_size, device, save_overlay):
    device=torch.device(device)
    model=UNet(3,3).to(device)
    ck=torch.load(weights, map_location=device)
    state=ck['model'] if isinstance(ck, dict) and 'model' in ck else ck
    model.load_state_dict(state); model.eval()
    out=Path(output_dir); (out/"raw_class_ids").mkdir(parents=True, exist_ok=True)
    (out/"color").mkdir(exist_ok=True); (out/"overlay").mkdir(exist_ok=True)

    exts={' .jpg', '.jpeg', '.png', '.bmp', '.tif', '.tiff'}
    with torch.no_grad():
        for p in sorted(Path(input_dir).iterdir()):
            if p.suffix.lower() not in exts: continue
            bgr=cv2.imread(str(p));
            if bgr is None: continue
            inp,(h,w),rgb=preprocess_bgr(bgr, img_size); inp=inp.to(device)
            logits=model(inp);
    pred=torch.argmax(logits,1).squeeze(0).cpu().numpy().astype(np.uint8)
    pred=cv2.resize(pred, (w,h), interpolation=cv2.INTER_NEAREST)
    col=decode(pred)
    cv2.imwrite(str(out/"raw_class_ids"/f"{p.stem}_pred.png"), pred)
    cv2.imwrite(str(out/"color"/f"{p.stem}_pred_color.png"),
    cv2.cvtColor(col, cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR))
    if save_overlay:
        over=overlay(rgb,col,0.5)
        cv2.imwrite(str(out/"overlay"/f"{p.stem}_overlay.png"),
    cv2.cvtColor(over, cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR))
    print(f"Saved {p.name}")

if __name__=='__main__':
    ap=argparse.ArgumentParser()
    ap.add_argument('--weights', required=True)
    ap.add_argument('--input_dir', required=True)
    ap.add_argument('--output_dir', default='inference_output')
    ap.add_argument('--img_size', type=int, default=512)
    ap.add_argument('--device', default='cuda' if torch.cuda.is_available() else
'cpu')
    ap.add_argument('--overlay', action='store_true')
    a=ap.parse_args(); run(a.weights, a.input_dir, a.output_dir, a.img_size,
a.device, a.overlay)

```

APPENDIX 5: evaluate.py (IoU metrics)

```

import argparse
from pathlib import Path
import torch
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader
import numpy as np
from dataset import FacadeDataset
from model import UNet

def compute_iou(preds, targets, nc=3):
    preds=preds.view(-1); targets=targets.view(-1); ious=[]
    for c in range(nc):
        pi=preds==c; ti=targets==c
        inter=(pi & ti).sum().item(); union=(pi|ti).sum().item()
        ious.append(float('nan') if union==0 else inter/union)
    return np.array(ious,dtype=np.float32), float(np.nanmean(ious))

if __name__=='__main__':
    ap=argparse.ArgumentParser(description='Evaluate mIoU on a folder')
    ap.add_argument('--weights', required=True)
    ap.add_argument('--images_dir', required=True)
    ap.add_argument('--masks_dir', required=True)
    ap.add_argument('--img_size', type=int, default=512)
    ap.add_argument('--batch_size', type=int, default=2)
    ap.add_argument('--device', default='cuda' if torch.cuda.is_available() else
'cpu')
    a=ap.parse_args()

    ds=FacadeDataset(a.images_dir, a.masks_dir, img_size=a.img_size)
    ld=DataLoader(ds, batch_size=a.batch_size, shuffle=False)
    dev=torch.device(a.device)
    m=UNet(3,3).to(dev)
    ck=torch.load(a.weights, map_location=dev)
    st=ck['model'] if isinstance(ck,dict) and 'model' in ck else ck
    m.load_state_dict(st); m.eval()

    preds_all=[]; targs_all=[]
    with torch.no_grad():
        for imgs, masks in ld:
            imgs=imgs.to(dev); masks=masks.to(dev)
            logits=m(imgs); preds=torch.argmax(logits,1)
            preds_all.append(preds.cpu()); targs_all.append(masks.cpu())
    preds_all=torch.cat(preds_all,0); targs_all=torch.cat(targs_all,0)
    per, miou=compute_iou(preds_all, targs_all)
    print('IoU (bg, stone, joint):', per)
    print('mIoU:', miou)

```

APPENDIX 6: generate_masks_sam.py

```

r"""
generate_masks_sam.py
One-pass stone masonry dataset maker using SAM.
- Saves stones, joints, and (optionally) an indexed mask in one run.
"""

import argparse, os, json, cv2, numpy as np
from tqdm import tqdm

# ----- CLI -----
def parse_args():
    p = argparse.ArgumentParser(description="One-pass SAM masonry dataset maker")
    p.add_argument("--images", required=True, help="Input photos folder")
    p.add_argument("--out", required=True, help="Output root")
    p.add_argument("--sam-type", default="vit_h", choices=["vit_h", "vit_l", "vit_b"])
    p.add_argument("--sam-ckpt", required=True, help="Path to SAM checkpoint .pth")
    # SAM thresholds
    p.add_argument("--pred-iou", type=float, default=0.86)
    p.add_argument("--stability", type=float, default=0.92)
    p.add_argument("--min-area", type=int, default=400)
    p.add_argument("--iou-thresh", type=float, default=0.6, help="IoU for simple NMS
to avoid heavy overlaps")
    # Large images
    p.add_argument("--max-long-side", type=int, default=2048,
                    help="Downscale so max(H,W)<=this; mask upscaled back (NEAREST)")
    # Outputs
    p.add_argument("--semantic", default="both", choices=["stone", "joints", "both"],
                    help="If not saving both, pick a single class")
    p.add_argument("--save-both", action="store_true", help="Save both stones and
joints")
    p.add_argument("--save-indexed", action="store_true", help="Also save
0=bg,1=stone,2=joint mask")
    p.add_argument("--copy-images", action="store_true", help="Copy originals to
out/images (PNG)")
    p.add_argument("--skip-existing", action="store_true", help="Skip if target files
exist")
    # ROI & post-processing
    p.add_argument("--roi-pad", type=float, default=0.03, help="Relative padding
around facade bbox (0..0.5)")
    p.add_argument("--min-roi", type=int, default=64, help="Minimum ROI size after
downscale")
    p.add_argument("--joint-dilate", type=int, default=0, help="Dilate joints by this
kernel (pixels) after upscaling")
    p.add_argument("--stone-close", type=int, default=0, help="Morph CLOSE kernel
(pixels) to fill tiny gaps in stones")
    # Optional contrast boost
    p.add_argument("--clahe", action="store_true", help="Apply CLAHE to L channel
before SAM")
    return p.parse_args()

# ----- IO -----
def collect_images(root):
    exts = {".jpg", ".jpeg", ".png", ".bmp", ".tif", ".tiff", ".webp"}
    files = []
    for dp, _, fn in os.walk(root):
        for f in fn:
            if os.path.splitext(f.lower())[1] in exts:
                files.append(os.path.join(dp, f))
    files.sort()
    return files

def imread_any(path):
    return cv2.imread(np.fromfile(path, dtype=np.uint8), cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)

```

```

def imwrite_png(path, img):
    os.makedirs(os.path.dirname(path), exist_ok=True)
    stem, ext = os.path.splitext(path)
    if ext.lower() != ".png":
        path = stem + ".png"
    if img.dtype != np.uint8:
        img = np.clip(img, 0, 255).astype(np.uint8)
    ok, buf = cv2.imencode(".png", img)
    if not ok:
        raise RuntimeError("cv2.imencode failed")
    with open(path, "wb") as f:
        f.write(buf.tobytes())

# ----- image utils -----
def ensure_uint8_3ch(img):
    if img is None:
        return None
    if img.dtype != np.uint8:
        if np.issubdtype(img.dtype, np.integer):
            info = np.iinfo(img.dtype)
            if info.max > 255:
                img = (img.astype(np.float32) * (255.0 / info.max)).round().clip(0,
255).astype(np.uint8)
            else:
                img = img.astype(np.uint8)
        else:
            img = np.clip(img, 0, 255).astype(np.uint8)
    if img.ndim == 2:
        img = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_GRAY2BGR)
    elif img.ndim == 3 and img.shape[2] == 4:
        img = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGRA2BGR)
    return np.ascontiguousarray(img)

def apply_clahe_bgr(img):
    lab = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2LAB)
    L, A, B = cv2.split(lab)
    clahe = cv2.createCLAHE(clipLimit=2.0, tileGridSize=(8,8))
    L2 = clahe.apply(L)
    lab2 = cv2.merge([L2, A, B])
    return cv2.cvtColor(lab2, cv2.COLOR_LAB2BGR)

# ----- NMS -----
def nms_binary_masks(masks, iou_thresh=0.6):
    kept = []
    for m in masks:
        keep = True
        for k in kept:
            inter = (m & k).sum()
            if inter == 0:
                continue
            uni = (m | k).sum()
            if uni == 0:
                continue
            if inter/uni >= iou_thresh:
                keep = False
                break
        if keep:
            kept.append(m)
    return kept

# ----- SAM -----
def load_sam(sam_type, ckpt, pred_iou, stability, min_area):
    try:

```

```

import torch
from segment_anything import sam_model_registry, SamAutomaticMaskGenerator
except Exception as e:
    raise SystemExit(
        "Install requirements first:\n"
        "  pip install opencv-python tqdm numpy\n"
        "  pip install --index-url https://download.pytorch.org/whl/cu121
torch==2.3.1 torchvision==0.18.1\n"
        "  pip install git+https://github.com/facebookresearch/segment-
anything.git\n"
        f"Original error: {e}"
    )
if not os.path.isfile(ckpt):
    raise SystemExit(f"SAM checkpoint not found: {ckpt}")

sam = sam_model_registry[sam_type](checkpoint=ckpt)
device = "cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu"
sam.to(device=device)

gen = SamAutomaticMaskGenerator(
    model=sam,
    points_per_side=16,          # up to 24 for more detail; 8 to save memory
    points_per_batch=64,
    crop_n_layers=0,
    crop_n_points_downscale_factor=2.0,
    pred_iou_thresh=pred_iou,
    stability_score_thresh=stability,
    min_mask_region_area=min_area,
    output_mode="binary_mask",
)
return gen

# ----- ROI + composition -----
def roi_bbox_from_union(u8, H, W, pad_ratio, min_size):
    ys, xs = np.where(u8 > 0)
    if len(xs) == 0:
        return 0, 0, W-1, H-1 # fallback: whole frame
    x0, x1 = xs.min(), xs.max()
    y0, y1 = ys.min(), ys.max()
    pad = int(round(max(H, W) * pad_ratio))
    x0 = max(0, x0 - pad); y0 = max(0, y0 - pad)
    x1 = min(W-1, x1 + pad); y1 = min(H-1, y1 + pad)
    # enforce minimum size
    if (x1 - x0 + 1) < min_size:
        cx = (x0 + x1) // 2
        x0 = max(0, cx - min_size // 2)
        x1 = min(W-1, x0 + min_size - 1)
    if (y1 - y0 + 1) < min_size:
        cy = (y0 + y1) // 2
        y0 = max(0, cy - min_size // 2)
        y1 = min(H-1, y0 + min_size - 1)
    return x0, y0, x1, y1

def compose_masks(union_small, Hs, Ws, roi_pad, min_roi):
    u8 = (union_small.astype(np.uint8) * 255)
    x0, y0, x1, y1 = roi_bbox_from_union(u8, Hs, Ws, roi_pad, min_roi)
    roi = np.zeros((Hs, Ws), np.uint8)
    roi[y0:y1+1, x0:x1+1] = 255
    roi_b = roi > 0
    stone_small = roi_b & union_small
    joints_small = roi_b & (~union_small)
    return stone_small, joints_small

# ----- main -----
def main():
    args = parse_args()
    files = collect_images(args.images)

```

```

if not files:
    raise SystemExit(f"No images in: {args.images}")

save_both = args.save_both or (args.semantic == "both")
if save_both:
    out_stone = os.path.join(args.out, "masks_stone")
    out_joints = os.path.join(args.out, "masks_joints")
    out_indexed = os.path.join(args.out, "masks_indexed") if args.save_indexed
else None
os.makedirs(out_stone, exist_ok=True)
os.makedirs(out_joints, exist_ok=True)
if out_indexed: os.makedirs(out_indexed, exist_ok=True)
else:
    out_masks = os.path.join(args.out, "masks")
    os.makedirs(out_masks, exist_ok=True)

out_images = None
if args.copy_images:
    out_images = os.path.join(args.out, "images")
    os.makedirs(out_images, exist_ok=True)

# meta
meta = {
    "sam_type": args.sam_type,
    "pred_iou": args.pred_iou,
    "stability": args.stability,
    "min_area": args.min_area,
    "iou_thresh": args.iou_thresh,
    "max_long_side": args.max_long_side,
    "roi_pad": args.roi_pad,
    "min_roi": args.min_roi,
    "joint_dilate": args.joint_dilate,
    "stone_close": args.stone_close,
    "clahe": args.clahe,
    "source": os.path.abspath(args.images),
    "save_both": save_both,
    "save_indexed": args.save_indexed,
}
with open(os.path.join(args.out, "meta.json"), "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
    json.dump(meta, f, indent=2, ensure_ascii=False)
if save_both and args.save_indexed:
    with open(os.path.join(args.out, "classes.json"), "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        json.dump(["background", "stone", "masonry_joint"], f, indent=2)
    with open(os.path.join(args.out, "palette.json"), "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        json.dump({"0": [0, 0, 0], "1": [200, 200, 200], "2": [255, 0, 0]}, f, indent=2)

gen = load_sam(args.sam_type, args.sam_ckpt, args.pred_iou, args.stability,
args.min_area)

def tidy(i):
    if i % 10 == 0:
        try:
            import gc, torch
            gc.collect()
            if torch.cuda.is_available():
                torch.cuda.empty_cache()
        except Exception:
            pass

for i, path in enumerate(tqdm(files, desc="SAM segmenting")):
    name = os.path.splitext(os.path.basename(path))[0]
    # skip checks

```

```

if save_both:
    if args.skip_existing and \
        os.path.isfile(os.path.join(out_stone, f"{name}.png")) and \
        os.path.isfile(os.path.join(out_joints, f"{name}.png")):
        continue
    else:
        target = os.path.join(out_masks, f"{name}.png")
        if args.skip_existing and os.path.isfile(target):
            continue

img = imread_any(path)
if img is None:
    print("Skip unreadable:", path); continue
img = ensure_uint8_3ch(img)
if args.clahe:
    img = apply_clahe_bgr(img)

H0, W0 = img.shape[:2]
if max(H0, W0) > args.max_long_side:
    s = args.max_long_side / float(max(H0, W0))
    newW = int(round(W0 * s)); newH = int(round(H0 * s))
    img_small = cv2.resize(img, (newW, newH), interpolation=cv2.INTER_LINEAR)
else:
    img_small = img
img_small = ensure_uint8_3ch(img_small)

masks_raw = gen.generate(img_small)
masks = [m["segmentation"].astype(bool) for m in masks_raw]
if masks:
    areas = [int(m.sum()) for m in masks]
    order = np.argsort(areas)[::-1]
    masks = [masks[j] for j in order]
    masks = nms_binary_masks(masks, iou_thresh=args.iou_thresh)
    union_small = np.any(np.stack(masks, 0), 0)
else:
    union_small = np.zeros(img_small.shape[:2], bool)

stone_s, joints_s = compose_masks(union_small, img_small.shape[0],
img_small.shape[1],
                                args.roi_pad, args.min_roi)

stone = cv2.resize(stone_s.astype(np.uint8), (W0, H0),
interpolation=cv2.INTER_NEAREST)
joints = cv2.resize(joints_s.astype(np.uint8), (W0, H0),
interpolation=cv2.INTER_NEAREST)

if args.stone_close and args.stone_close > 0:
    k = int(args.stone_close); k = max(1, k | 1)
    kernel = cv2.getStructuringElement(cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE, (k, k))
    stone = cv2.morphologyEx(stone*255, cv2.MORPH_CLOSE, kernel); stone =
(stone > 0).astype(np.uint8)
if args.joint_dilate and args.joint_dilate > 0:
    k = int(args.joint_dilate); k = max(1, k | 1)
    kernel = cv2.getStructuringElement(cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE, (k, k))
    joints = cv2.dilate(joints*255, kernel, iterations=1); joints = (joints
> 0).astype(np.uint8)

# save
if save_both:
    imwrite_png(os.path.join(out_stone, f"{name}.png"), stone*255)
    imwrite_png(os.path.join(out_joints, f"{name}.png"), joints*255)
    if args.save_indexed:
        idx = np.zeros((H0, W0), np.uint8)
        idx[stone > 0] = 1
        idx[joints > 0] = 2
        imwrite_png(os.path.join(out_indexed, f"{name}.png"), idx)
else:

```

```
sem = stone if args.semantic == "stone" else joints
imwrite_png(os.path.join(out_masks, f"{name}.png"), sem*255)

if out_images is not None:
    imwrite_png(os.path.join(out_images, f"{name}.png"), img)

tidy(i)

print("Done.")
if save_both:
    print("Stones:", os.path.join(args.out, "masks_stone"))
    print("Joints:", os.path.join(args.out, "masks_joints"))
    if args.save_indexed:
        print("Indexed:", os.path.join(args.out, "masks_indexed"))
else:
    print("Masks:", os.path.join(args.out, "masks"))
if out_images is not None:
    print("Images:", os.path.join(args.out, "images"))

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

targs_all=[]
```

APPENDIX 7: project_masks_to_pointcloud.py

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
"""
project_masks_to_pointcloud.py (multiclass)
Project 2D indexed masks (0..K-1) onto a 3D point cloud using COLMAP cameras.
Aggregates votes per class across views and assigns the argmax class.

Inputs:
--cloud cloud.ply
--masks <dir> (indexed PNGs from assemble_multiclass_masks.py)
--colmap-cameras cameras.txt
--colmap-images images.txt
--classes-json classes.json (from the assembler; maps class name -> index)

Output:
segmented_cloud.ply (colored by palette if provided)
per-point labels CSV (optional)

Requirements:
open3d, numpy, opencv-python
"""
import argparse, os, sys, json, numpy as np, cv2
import open3d as o3d

def parse_args():
    p = argparse.ArgumentParser(description="Project indexed 2D masks to 3D point
cloud (COLMAP)")
    p.add_argument("--cloud", required=True)
    p.add_argument("--masks", required=True)
    p.add_argument("--colmap-cameras", required=True)
    p.add_argument("--colmap-images", required=True)
    p.add_argument("--classes-json", required=True)
    p.add_argument("--palette-json", default="", help="Optional JSON mapping class-
>RGB for coloring")
    p.add_argument("--out-cloud", default="segmented_cloud.ply")
    p.add_argument("--depth-tolerance", type=float, default=0.01)
    p.add_argument("--render-point-size", type=float, default=3.0)
    p.add_argument("--save-per-point-labels", default="")
    return p.parse_args()

def read_cameras_txt(path):
    cams = {}
    with open(path, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        for line in f:
            line=line.strip()
            if not line or line.startswith("#"): continue
            parts = line.split()
            cam_id = int(parts[0]); model = parts[1]; width = int(parts[2]);
height=int(parts[3])
            params = list(map(float, parts[4:]))
            K = intrinsics_from_colmap(model, params, width, height)
            cams[cam_id] = {"K":K, "width":width, "height":height, "model":model,
"params":params}
    return cams

def intrinsics_from_colmap(model, p, w, h):
    K = np.eye(3, dtype=np.float64)
    if model in ("SIMPLE_PINHOLE", "SIMPLE_RADIAL", "RADIAL"):
        f, cx, cy = p[0], p[1], p[2]
        K[0,0]=f; K[1,1]=f; K[0,2]=cx; K[1,2]=cy
    elif model == "PINHOLE":
        fx, fy, cx, cy = p[0], p[1], p[2], p[3]
        K[0,0]=fx; K[1,1]=fy; K[0,2]=cx; K[1,2]=cy
    elif model in ("OPENCV", "FULL_OPENCV", "OPENCV_FISHEYE"):
```

```

        fx, fy, cx, cy = p[0], p[1], p[2], p[3]
        K[0,0]=fx; K[1,1]=fy; K[0,2]=cx; K[1,2]=cy
    else:
        raise NotImplementedError(f"Unsupported COLMAP camera model: {model}")
    return K

def read_images_txt(path):
    images = []
    with open(path, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        lines = [l.strip() for l in f if l.strip() and not l.startswith("#")]
    i=0
    while i < len(lines):
        parts = lines[i].split()
        img_id = int(parts[0])
        qw,qx,qy,qz = map(float, parts[1:5])
        tx,ty,tz = map(float, parts[5:8])
        cam_id = int(parts[8])
        name = " ".join(parts[9:])

    images.append({"id":img_id,"q":[qw,qx,qy,qz],"t":np.array([tx,ty,tz],dtype=np.float
64),"cam_id":cam_id,"name":name})
        i+=1
        if i<len(lines): i+=1
    return images

def qvec2rotmat(q):
    qw,qx,qy,qz = q
    return np.array([
        [1-2*qy*qy-2*qz*qz, 2*qx*qy-2*qz*qw, 2*qx*qz+2*qy*qw],
        [2*qx*qy+2*qz*qw, 1-2*qx*qx-2*qz*qz, 2*qy*qz-2*qx*qw],
        [2*qx*qz-2*qy*qw, 2*qy*qz+2*qx*qw, 1-2*qx*qx-2*qy*qy]
    ], dtype=np.float64)

def project_points(K, R, t, X):
    Xc = (R @ X.T + t[:,None]).T
    uvw = (K @ Xc.T).T
    uv = uvw[:, :2] / uvw[:, 2:3]
    return uv, Xc[:,2]

def render_depth_from_cloud(pcd, width, height, K, R, t, point_size=3.0):
    intrinsic = o3d.camera.PinholeCameraIntrinsic(width, height, K[0,0], K[1,1],
K[0,2], K[1,2])
    extrinsic = np.eye(4); extrinsic[:3,:3] = R; extrinsic[:3,3] = t
    renderer = o3d.visualization.rendering.OffscreenRenderer(width, height)
    scene = renderer.scene
    mat = o3d.visualization.rendering.MaterialRecord()
    mat.shader = "defaultUnlit"; mat.point_size = float(point_size)
    scene.add_geometry("pcd", pcd, mat)
    scene.camera.set_projection(intrinsic, 0.01, 1000.0, width, height)
    scene.camera.set_view_matrix(extrinsic)
    depth = renderer.render_to_depth_image(False)
    depth_np = np.asarray(depth, dtype=np.float32)
    depth_np[depth_np==0] = np.inf
    return depth_np

def main():
    args = parse_args()
    pcd = o3d.io.read_point_cloud(args.cloud)
    if len(pcd.points)==0: print("Empty cloud"); sys.exit(1)
    P = np.asarray(pcd.points)

    cams = read_cameras_txt(args.colmap_cameras)
    imgs = read_images_txt(args.colmap_images)
    by_name = {im["name"]: im for im in imgs}

```

```

with open(args.classes_json, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
    class_to_idx = json.load(f)
num_classes = 1 + max(class_to_idx.values())

# optional palette
palette = {}
if args.palette_json and os.path.isfile(args.palette_json):
    with open(args.palette_json, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        palette = json.load(f)

# votes per class
votes = np.zeros((len(P), num_classes), dtype=np.int32)

# Iterate over masks (indexed PNGs)
mask_files = [f for f in os.listdir(args.masks) if
os.path.isfile(os.path.join(args.masks, f))]
for mf in mask_files:
    if mf not in by_name:
        print(f"[WARN] No COLMAP pose for mask: {mf}"); continue
    rec = by_name[mf]
    cam = cams[rec["cam_id"]]; K=cam["K"]; W=cam["width"]; H=cam["height"]

    mpath = os.path.join(args.masks, mf)
    mask = cv2.imread(mpath, cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
    if mask is None:
        print("[WARN] unreadable mask:", mpath); continue
    if mask.ndim == 3: mask = mask[:, :, 0] # keep first channel if needed
    if (mask.shape[1], mask.shape[0]) != (W, H):
        mask = cv2.resize(mask, (W, H), interpolation=cv2.INTER_NEAREST)

    R = qvec2rotmat(rec["q"]); t = rec["t"]
    depth = render_depth_from_cloud(pcd, W, H, K, R, t, args.render_point_size)

    uv, z = project_points(K, R, t, P)
    u = np.round(uv[:, 0]).astype(int)
    v = np.round(uv[:, 1]).astype(int)
    inside = (u >= 0) & (u < W) & (v >= 0) & (v < H) & (z > 0)
    idx = np.where(inside)[0]
    if len(idx) == 0: continue

    z_img = depth[v[idx], u[idx]]
    visible = np.isfinite(z_img) & (np.abs(z[idx] - z_img) <= args.depth_tolerance)

    # accumulate class votes
    pix_vals = mask[v[idx], u[idx]].astype(np.int32)
    valid = visible & (pix_vals >= 0) & (pix_vals < num_classes)
    sel_idx = idx[valid]
    sel_vals = pix_vals[valid]
    # votes[point, class] += 1 per observation
    np.add.at(votes, (sel_idx, sel_vals), 1)

# decide label by argmax; background assumed index 0
labels = votes.argmax(axis=1).astype(np.uint8)

# colorize
colors = np.zeros((len(P), 3), dtype=np.float64)
# default colors if palette missing
default_rgb = {
    0: [0.15, 0.15, 0.15], # background dark
    1: [1.0, 1.0, 1.0], # stone white
    2: [0.78, 0.78, 0.0], # joint yellowish
    3: [0.0, 0.5, 1.0], # door
    4: [0.0, 1.0, 1.0], # window
    5: [1.0, 0.0, 0.0], # roof
}
# build map index->rgb

```

```
idx_to_rgb = {}
for name, idx in class_to_idx.items():
    if args.palette_json and name in palette:
        rgb = np.array(palette[name], dtype=np.float64)/255.0
    else:
        rgb = np.array(default_rgb.get(idx, [0.8,0.8,0.8]), dtype=np.float64)
    idx_to_rgb[idx] = rgb

for i in range(len(P)):
    colors[i] = idx_to_rgb.get(int(labels[i]), np.array([0.8,0.8,0.8]))

pcd.colors = o3d.utility.Vector3dVector(colors)
o3d.io.write_point_cloud(args.out_cloud, pcd, write_ascii=False)
print("Wrote:", args.out_cloud)

if args.save_per_point_labels:
    import csv
    with open(args.save_per_point_labels, "w", newline="") as f:
        w = csv.writer(f); w.writerow(["index","label"])
        for i,l in enumerate(labels): w.writerow([i,int(l)])

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```